

EDEN ISS

System Requirements Document

prepared for

WP 2.1 - System Requirements & Interface Analysis

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			<p>(door, Roxtec interface panels etc.).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• S-240 and FEG-1040. Determined as not hard requirements. Emergency set of climate clothing does not need to be available near the emergency exit door in the MTF at all times. Personnel can even in worst conditions survive the 400 m distance to the NM-III in normal clothing.
1.11	2018-09-28	See list of authors	<p>Added Annex A: System Requirements Verification Control Document.</p> <p>Final release version.</p>

Executive summary

This document provides the system requirements of the EDEN ISS project.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AD	Applicable Document	ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack
AS	Aero Sekur S.p.A.	LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology
ADS	Airbus Defence and Space	MTF	Mobile Test Facility
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research	NDS	Nutrient Delivery System
BLSS	Bio-regenerative Life Support Systems	PBAR	Plant Biologically Active Radiation
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	RD	Reference Document
DLO	Wageningen University and Research	TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A.
DLR	German Aerospace Center	TBC	To Be Confirmed
ECC	EDEN ISS Control Centre	TBD	To Be Determined
EDR	European Drawer Rack	TPZ	Telespazio S.p.A.
EP	Elevated Platform	TRL	Technology Readiness Level
ES	EnginSoft S.p.A.	SS	Service Section
ESA	European Space Agency	UIP	Utility Interface Panel
ESC	External Storage Container	UoG	University of Guelph
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	WP	Work Package
HS	Heliospectra BA		

1 Introduction

1.1 Overall objectives of the EDEN ISS project

Long-term human presence in space will require the development of bio-regenerative life support systems (BLSS). The integration of such systems into manned habitats decreases the resupply requirements by generating human resources via biological processes. The EDEN ISS project aims to validate selected subsystems and key technologies up to a TRL of 6 according to the standards described in the Technology Readiness Levels Handbook for Space Applications of the European Space Agency (ESA) [RD1]. Therefore the project will demonstrate operational capability of key technologies in an environment with some characteristics relevant to space. For this purpose a dedicated test campaign will be executed at the Neumayer Station III in Antarctica where a deployed mobile test facility will be operated by an isolated overwintering crew. This deployment will also be preparatory research for a future plant production system at the ISS.

The main objectives of EDEN ISS are shown in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1: Objectives of the EDEN ISS project.

Objective 1	Manufacturing a space analogue mobile test facility to provide representative mass flows and proper test environments for plant cultivation technologies as an essential on-ground preparatory activity for future space exploration.
Objective 2	Integration and test of key elements for plant cultivation in 1) an ISPR-like system (International Standard Payload Rack) for future test on-board ISS and 2) a Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG) to prepare for closed-loop bio-regenerative life support systems.
Objective 3	Adaption, integration, fine-tuning and demonstration of key technologies and their functionality in respective laboratory environments and (under highly isolated conditions) in an Antarctic environment.
Objective 4	Development and demonstration of operation techniques and processes for higher plant cultivation to achieve reliable and safe production of high-quality food.
Objective 5	Study of microbial behavior and countermeasures in plant-based closed ecosystems and their impacts on isolated crews.
Objective 6	Actively advancing knowledge related to human spaceflight and transformation of research results into terrestrial applications , by actively leveraging synergies between space and non-space consortium partners.

1.2 Summary state-of-the-art: Bio-regenerative life support systems and architecture

The unique aspect of EDEN ISS is the focus on the key technologies and procedures associated with higher plant cultivation and high quality safe food production. This means that instead of dealing with all the different aspects of a BLSS, the envisioned project focuses on an essential target area. Targeting only this area guarantees a higher scientific outcome than spreading the research focus too broadly. Therefore, the EDEN ISS consortium will advance the current state-of-the-art through several means:

- Develop a **high fidelity ISPR cultivation system with approximately 1 m² production area**, thereby enhancing the feasibility of Europe providing the ISS with a plant production facility capable of almost an order of magnitude increase to current orbit production areas.
- Deploy a European constructed, **highly integrated, mobile greenhouse module test facility to Antarctica**. After completion of the project, the test facility will be used for further on-going BLSS investigations and will be open for experiments to the European BLSS community.
- Increase the TRL of a **microgravity NDS** built with materials capable of reducing possible biological contamination and including **advanced on-line ion-selective sensors**.
- Advance the TRL of **spectrally tunable LED lighting systems** for highly reliable and remotely operated plant production systems. Energy conservation will be improved through the development and use of **advanced LED heat capture techniques and intra-canopy lighting**. Experimentally determine

optimal light recipes for 5-10 crops and employ these recipes to maximize production within the mobile test facility.

- Increase of the TRL of relevant technologies in the field of **bio-detection and decontamination** of BLSS.
- Further develop proper **plant handling and food safety procedures** for higher plant cultivation in closed systems comparable to ISS and future long-duration space missions.

Table 1-2 provides a summary of the specific advances to the current state-of-the-art for the primary focus areas of the EDEN ISS project.

Table 1-2: Overview and comparison between state-of-the-art and beyond state-of-the-art.

System	State-of-the-art	Beyond state-of-the-art
Greenhouse module test facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple ‘Salad Machines’, small food quantities • Cultivation processes and plant health monitoring is rather hands-on with limited automation • Bulk of Antarctic systems have been expeditioner/hobby- based and constructed with materials found on-site • Limited to no remote commanding • Single surface production systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce higher quantities of fresh crops in order to achieve higher mission fidelity • Highly integrated test module, considering all necessary subsystems and analyzing the overall mass production principles • Detailed quantification of pre- and post-processing analysis, cleaning and general crew time allocations • Enhance reliability of remote greenhouses through telepresence (tools and competency)
ISS plant production facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small-scale production areas (~0.1 m²) • Science driven • Negligible food production • Low to marginal environmental control reliability (some exceptions) • Non-scalable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium-scale production areas (~1 m²) • Food production and psychological benefit driven • Non-negligible food production for repeatable safety evaluation • Well characterized and reliable environmental control • Scalable
Nutrient delivery system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil-based and soilless cultivation • On-line nutrient solution status measurements are indiscriminate (e.g. electrical conductivity) • Off-line measurements of ion-selective values are time intensive (e.g. days/ weeks) • Difficult and insufficient bio-contamination prevention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soilless cultivation is imperative • Higher yield, low water and nutrient use systems • Real-time online measurements of selective ion concentrations (e.g. new optrodes) • View of root system enhances ability of remote telemetric monitoring (e.g. aeroponic) • Nanostructured coatings for bio-contamination prevention onto surfaces
Light system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct natural light (Sun) not feasible for space greenhouses (e.g. radiation, temporal variability, system complexity) • Fluorescent, high pressure sodium, metal halide, Sulphur plasma lamp, induction lamp • PAR-specific multispectral LED light most promising candidate, but in early development stage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High performance LEDs (combining a variety of monochromatic lights, specifically tailored to plant photosynthetic requirements) • Highly integrated panels and optimized with respect to mass, thermal load (active cooled), volume, and power demand • Intra-canopy lighting systems
Bio-detection and decontamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bio-detection performed by classical sampling method, wiping followed by incubation in a sample medium • Work intensive spray and wipe decontamination procedures, physico-chemical treatment or steam disinfection of small items • No possibility to disinfect hard-to-reach areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time detection of quality and quantity of microbial loads (using gas-analyzing instrument E-Nose) • High reachability (e.g. cavities, tubes and harnesses) with TransMADDS • Specific decontaminant depending on the microbial load, preventive effect, no damage of equipment
Food quality and safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensory evaluation of food products for characterization of texture, flavor and palatability • Nutrient determination via solvent extraction and analysis via laboratory scale atomic absorption spectroscopy, liquid chromatography and UV-Visible spectroscopy • Lab based PCR or standard plate count techniques and microscopy employed for identification of microbial and infectious agents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish sensor panel response versus physio-metric data analysis to produce a sensory evaluation protocol for use on board ISS • Rapid, non-destructive indicators of food quality • Rapid screen for microbial contamination • Food safety quick tests; new palatability analysis tools • Increase shelf lifetime for produced crops

2 Terms, definitions, conventions

2.1 Definitions and terms

Figure 2-1: Overview of EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility (MTF) main elements.

EDEN ISS Elements

Mobile Test Facility (MTF)

The EDEN ISS mobile test facility to be operated in the Antarctic at the Neumayer Station III for testing a food production system under mission relevant conditions at ISS and future planetary outposts. The MTF comprises 2 x 20 ft high-cube shipping containers joined together at their front ends. The MTF is oriented in East-West direction. The East container is called the Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG) and the West container the Service Section (SS) (see Figure 2-1).

Service Section Container

The Service Section Container houses the main entrance at its West front end, which leads into the cold porch (or air lock) and from there on into the Service Section. The East front end of the Service Section Container is connected to the West front end of the FEG Container (see Figure 2-1). The Service Section Container also contains a raised floor on which the nor-

	<p><i>mal working area is located. The space below the raised floor is called the sub-floor.</i></p>
Cold Porch	<p><i>An enclosed section in the Service Section Container of the MTF that provides a climatic interface buffer between the external environment and the MTF Service Section (see Figure 2-1). Used for changing clothing (weather gear to lab clothing), general storage and housing the waste liquid and fresh water tank in the sub-floor.</i></p>
Service Section (SS)	<p><i>The service section is housed in the Service Section Container (see Figure 2-1). The Service Section houses the ISPR cultivation system. Furthermore, the Service Section contains all utilities for the MTF such as power distribution, Air Management System, Thermal Control System, Nutrient Delivery System, and consoles/computers for controlling MTF, FEG and ISPR. The SS also provides a work environment for visiting personnel including desk/chair/locker and sink.</i></p>
International Standard Payload Rack (ISPR) Cultivation System	<p><i>The EDEN ISS ISPR is a ground version of the standard payload racks used on ISS. It provides all resources such as power, environmental and thermal control, nutrient delivery and data management to support 2 plant cultivation chambers for simultaneous cultivation of different plants under different environmental conditions.</i></p>
FEG Container	<p><i>The FEG Container houses the Future Exploration Greenhouse. The West front end of the FEG Container is connected to the East front end of the Service Section Container. The East front end of the FEG Container houses an emergency exit. The FEG Container also contains a raised floor on which the normal working area is located. The space below the raised floor is called the sub-floor.</i></p>
Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG)	<p><i>The FEG is installed within the FEG Container. It contains rack structures mounted along the sides of the container (4 each side). Each rack can be configured with up to 4 shelves for accommodating Plant Grow Units, LED lighting, LED water cooling, nutrient delivery hardware, sensors and cameras. Also contains space in a rack for seed germination and general storage. The FEG is separated from the SS by a sealed wall. A door is provided for access from the SS. An Emergency Exit door is available at the far end of the FEG.</i></p>
<u>MTF Internal – General</u>	
Raised Floor	<p><i>Both containers of the MTF have a raised floor which is around 30 cm above the original container floor. The raised floor is held by a stainless steel structure</i></p>

and is the normal walking and working surface, therefore the stainless steel framework is covered with floor panels. The space below the raised floor is called the sub-floor.

Sub-Floor	<i>Space between container floor and raised floor. The free height of the subfloor is around 25 cm throughout the whole MTF. The sub-floor contains the fresh and waste water tanks inside the cold porch and air tubes and liquid pipes within the Service Section and the FEG. The sub-floor also contains a drainage basin in the Service Section and the FEG.</i>
Floor Panels	<i>The floor panels cover the raised floor and functions as the normal walking and working surface.</i>
Drainage Basin (= "sump")	<i>The drainage basin is located in the sub-floor of the Service Section and the FEG. Its purpose is to collect spilled or leaked fluids. Collected liquids are drained via pump to waste liquid tank housed in cold porch sub-floor.</i>
Wall and Ceiling Cladding	<i>Interior wall panelling that protects the MTF insulation from humidity and spilled liquids.</i>
Container-to-Container Interface	<i>Insulated space between containers for mating joints, utility piping, electric/sensor harness connectors etc.</i>

MTF Internal – Cold Porch

Main Entrance Door	<i>Main door for access to MTF. Weather sealed door with small window.</i>
Cold Porch Heaters	<i>Heater(s) in the cold porch that automatically are ON when Cold Porch ambient temperature falls below 5°C.</i>
Cold Porch locker	<i>Container for clothing, personnel items etc. (external weather gear, lab clothing etc.).</i>
Waste Liquid Fluid Tank	<i>300 l (approx.) tank housed in sub-floor of the Cold Porch for temporary storage of all liquid waste from the MTF.</i>
Fresh Water Tank	<i>300 l (approx.) tank housed in sub-floor of the Cold Porch for storage of fresh water for the MTF.</i>

MTF Internal – Service Section

Service Section Entrance Door	<i>Door connecting the cold porch with the Service Section.</i>
Service Section General Lighting	<i>Overhead white light source fulfilling standard for office illumination at desk level.</i>
Service Section Window	<i>Rectangular window on the North side of the Service Section above desk facing the NM-III.</i>
Atmosphere Management System (AMS)	<i>The AMS is an automatically system that actively controls a pre-determined air flow speed, temperature</i>

and composition to the FEG via air ducts and dedicated louvers. FEG atmospheric parameters monitored by the AMS are CO₂, temperature and relative humidity. Exhaust air is cycled back to the AMS from the FEG via air ducts. The AMS then controls the humidity, and temperature of the returned airflow and sterilizes using UV and filters with a combination of a pre-filter, HEPA and charcoal filter (e.g., for ethylene) prior to cycling back to the FEG (which, to the extent possible, has a closed atmospheric environment). The AMS also has a separate Service Section air control system ('fresh air system'), which uses external air drawn into the Cold Porch and subsequently passed to the Service Section as a source of fresh air (controlled for temperature and humidity).

Argus

The Argus System is an all-in-one hardware and software platform for instrumentation monitoring, data acquisition, data logging, alarms, and automated equipment control. EDEN ISS uses Argus for monitoring and control of the Nutrient Delivery System, Atmosphere Management System, Thermal Control System and overall MTF system.

Nutrient Delivery System (NDS)

An automatic system for supplying nutrient feed to the Plant Cultivation Units in the FEG. The NDS comprises 2 individual bulk nutrient solutions that can be automatically modified with respect to acid, base and nutrient salt concentration prior to being pumped to the FEG Plant Cultivation Units. The NDS monitors and controls the nutrient composition for electrical conductivity (EC), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, ion-selective concentrations (specific ions), temperature and ozone concentration (measurement in air - for safety purposes). The bulk nutrient solutions are stored in two 250 L tanks. Fresh water is supplied to the nutrient mixing system from an approximate 300 L tank. Waste liquids are pumped to the waste tank in the subfloor of the Cold Porch. The NDS is monitored and controlled via the Argus computer.

Nutrient Tank(s)

Two 250 L tanks each containing a specific bulk nutrient solution for the Nutrient Delivery System (NDS).

Power Distribution System

The Power Distribution System (PDS) distributes a stabilized 230 VAC power supply to all of the MTF elements requiring electrical power. The PDS also provides 24 VDC and 12 VDC power to selective systems such as the ISPR. The PDS is connected to the Neumayer Station III overall electrical power supply of 230 VAC by land cable.

Thermal Control System (TCS)

The Thermal Control System (TCS) provides individual water-cooling for the Atmosphere Management Sys-

tem (AMS), the ISPR and the LED panels in the FEG Plant Grow Units. The TCS provides water to each of these cooling loops at a pre-defined temperature. The return flow temperature is monitored by the TCS and automatically adjusts the flow rate to assure sufficient cooling. Waste heat is removed via heat exchangers in each TCS loop and cycled outside of the MTF via separate fluid loops (water + Tyfocor) to a passive external radiator mounted on the top of the MTF. The TCS is monitored and controlled via the Argus computer.

Uninterruptible Power Supply

The Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) provides emergency power to specific systems in case of main power failure from the Neumayer Station III. Presently designed to provide 1400 W for 36 – 115 minutes (depending on number of modules) at 70% load.

MTF Internal – ISPR

ISPR Cold Plate

A water cooled plate for mounting items that need removal of excess heat during operation.

ISPR Drawer

A dedicated removable drawer in the ISPR for housing payloads. Each drawer is provided with standard interface resources such as power, thermal cooling, data handling etc. The number of available drawers is dependent upon the design function of the ISPR

ISPR Fire Alarm LED

Red LED smoke/fire light on front of ISPR that is activated by interior smoke sensor in case of fire.

LabVIEW

LabVIEW (Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench) is a system-design platform and development environment for a visual programming language from National Instruments. The EDEN ISS ISPR uses this application for monitoring and control of all the ISPR sensor parameters.

Plant Cultivation Chamber

A dedicated plant grow unit housed in a drawer of the ISPR. There are 2x chambers in the ISPR, one for short plants and one for tall plants. Each chamber contains a root zone, a plant growth zone and a LED illumination panel. Each chamber has provision for nutrient feed to the root zone, CO₂ and fresh air to the plant zone as well as water cooling and electrical power for the LEDs. The chambers are monitored by sensors via the ISPR LabVIEW computer application software for CO₂ and relative humidity in the plant growth zone as well as soil temperature, moisture, and electrical conductivity in the root zone. Two video cameras are provided in each chamber to monitor overall plant health.

Rack Maintenance Switch

A 2-position manually operated switch that when set in open position cuts all power to ISPR. Used to assure

Utility Interface Panel (UIP)	<i>safety of personnel when accessing inside of ISPR for maintenance purposes etc.</i> <i>Interface panel at base of ISPR for connecting external utilities such as water, power, data etc. via ISPR standard connectors.</i>
<u>Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG)</u>	
FEG Entrance Door	<i>Door connecting Service Section with the Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG).</i>
Emergency Exit	<i>Weather sealed door that connects FEG to exterior platform. During normal operations only to be used during fire or chemical emergency if path to main door in Cold Porch is not accessible (may be used during the for basic facility access during the construction and test phases).</i>
FEG General Lighting	<i>Overhead dimmable white light source fulfilling standard for office illumination at desk level.</i>
Aeroponics	<i>Aeroponics is the process of growing plants in an air or mist environment without the use of soil or an aggregate medium.</i>
Hydroponics	<i>Hydroponics is a subset of hydroculture and is a method of growing plants using mineral nutrient solutions, in water, without soil. Terrestrial plants may be grown with their roots in the mineral nutrient solution only, or in an inert medium, such as perlite or gravel.</i>
LED Panel	<i>A single LED lamp with variable light output from 150 - 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ and individual wavelength setting all controlled by Ethernet commanding/monitoring via Argus computer in Service Section. The lamps are water cooled via the MTF Thermal Control System. One LED panel is utilized per single Plant Growth Unit (except in the instance of intracanopy lighting).</i>
Photosynthetically Active Radiation	<i>The Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) designates the spectral range (wave band) of solar radiation from 400 to 700 nanometers that photosynthetic organisms are able to use in the process of photosynthesis.</i>
Louver	<i>An opening in the incoming FEG air ducts that can be manually controlled to manipulate the airflow in the plants. Each horizontal FEG air duct includes 4 louvers.</i>

Figure 2-2: Overview of Plant Grow Unit components and topology of FEG Plant Grow Racks.

Plant Grow Chamber

An alternative terminology for the interior of the FEG.

Plant Grow Rack

A standard rack structure in the FEG comprising shelves for accommodating the Plant Grow Units. There are in total eight Plant Grow Racks in the FEG, four on the left (North) side and four on the right (South) side. Each rack is individually numbered as follows:

When facing Emergency Exit from FEG door, the racks on the left (North) side are numbered L1, L2, L3 and L4, those on the right (South) side R1, R2, R3 and R4. Each rack can be individually configured with up to 8 Plant Grow Units (see Figure 2-2).

Plant Growth Level

The level in the Plant Grow Unit that separates the plant root volume in the Plant Grow Trays from the plant foliage section (see Figure 2-2).

Plant Grow Unit

A standard plant growth dedicated volume available in various heights (52 cm, 104 cm and 208 cm) dependent on plant size. The unit comprises from top to bottom; an LED panel with water cooling, a plant leaf section, a Plant Grow Tray with holes for shoots and a root zone with an aeroponics nutrient delivery system.

Each Unit is numbered either 1, 2, 3 or 4 from bottom to top depending on configuration. For example the first rack on the left side has 4 Plant Grow Units and is therefore numbered L1-1, L1-2, L1-3 and L1-4 from bottom to top.

Plant Grow Tray

A standard plant growing tray, 40 cm by 60 cm, comprises an enclosed lower Root Zone section for hous-

ing the plant root system and nutrient delivery diffusers. The upper surface of the Root Zone section has various hole sizes/number depending on plant height/species and is termed the Shoot Zone (see Figure 2-2).

Seed Germination Unit

A dedicated unit for germinating seeds prior to transfer of shoots to Plant Grow Units. Will be housed in the left-hand side end rack, position L4 (see Figure 2-2).

Mobile Platform

The Mobile Platform is a robotic arm that provides a mount for monitoring a fluorescent imaging camera and an infrared camera in the FEG for monitoring individual plant health status. The robotic arm is fixed to a ceiling mounted track running the length of the FEG. The camera platform can be manoeuvred to individual Plant Grow Units by controlling both the vertical and horizontal position of the arm.

MTF External

Platform External Walkway

Walkway on platform around the perimeter of the MTF.

Safety Railing

Railing for safety purposes on sides of MTF access stairs, platform walkway perimeter, and a portion of the MTF roof (TBC).

MTF Access Stairs

Stairway with safety rails allowing personnel access from ground to elevated platform level and the MTF entrance hatch.

Door Lighting

Lighting mounted over the top of the main entrance and the emergency exit doors to illuminate the space in front of the respective door.

Platform External Lighting

Fixed lighting around perimeter of MTF.

MTF Roof Access Ladder

Vertical ladder for access to roof of MTF mounted (but likely to be transportable) on the West side of the West-container to the right of the main entrance.

External Radiator(s)

Radiators for excess heat dissipation from internal MTF thermal control system. Heat load from MTF transported to radiator via fluid line. Fluid qualified down to -50 degC.

WLAN Antenna

Wireless LAN antenna for data communications between MTF and NM-III housed externally on MTF container roof.

External Utility Connector(s) (EUC)

The EUC(s) provide for MTF external connector(s) for power (MAIN power, 1x cable), data (optical cable), fire alarm cable to NM-III, waste liquid (valve), and wireless LAN antenna for data communications between MTF and NM-III.

Neumayer Station III (NM-III)

NM-III	<i>Neumayer Station III - permanently manned German Antarctic research facility</i>
External Storage Container (ESC)	<i>Cold storage container(s) for spares, utilities etc. 7 - 8 km from NM-III. The ESC has no environmental control system and hence stored items need to be compliant with extreme Antarctic ambient climate parameters.</i>
NM-III EDEN ISS Control Console(s)	<i>EDEN ISS monitoring/commanding console(s) in the NM-III.</i>
Multipurpose Laboratory	<i>Facility in NM-III to perform food sample processing, plant sample drying and housing EDEN ISS freezer, analysis equipment, chemical reagents etc. The multipurpose laboratory provides a floor space of ca. 25 m² and the left side of the lab (upon entry) will be devoted to EDEN ISS activities. Space in the laboratory may be somewhat restrictive during summer field seasons but upon departure of the austral summer field team, a greater space within the laboratory will be available.</i>
Freezer Storage Facility	<i>Either EDEN ISS dedicated plant sample freezer or NM-III general freezer.</i>
Chemical Storage Facility	<i>NM-III facility for safe storage of EDEN ISS chemicals such as nutrient salts, acids, bases and disinfection chemicals.</i>
Skidoos	<i>Motorized manned sledge for access to external storage container up to 10 km from NM-III</i>
Transport Sledge	<i>EDEN ISS dedicated manual sledge for transporting supplies waste etc. between NM-III and MTF.</i>
Polarstern Crane	<i>Crane on the research vessel Polarstern for off-loading up to 25000 kg</i>
NM-III Crane	<i>Mobile crane at Neumayer Station III to be used for constructing Elevated Platform and MTF. Maximum load 10000 kg</i>
Elevated Platform (EP)	<i>The EP is a platform raised 2.5 m above ground level for mounting the MTF containers. The platform is reached from ground level by an inclined stairway. The platform is raised to reduce snow accumulation around the MTF.</i>

Other Terms

DLR Control Center	<i>Main control center for EDEN ISS at the DLR, Bremen, Germany, for monitoring MTF science and house-keeping data and issuing commands.</i>
User Home Base	<i>Remote EDEN ISS user facility for monitoring science and house-keeping data and issuing commands.</i>

E-Nose

An electronic sensor for detecting chemical off-gassing signature of pathogens such as E. coli and Salmonella Spp. Used in EDEN ISS project to monitor plant health status prior to human consumption.

TransMADDS

An aerosol based decontamination and disinfection system for sterilizing enclosed volumes of potential pathogens harmful to both plant and human health. Use in EDEN ISS dependent on concentration of pathogens detected by E-Nose and/or swabs/culture growths.

2.2 Conventions

2.2.1 Units

The International System of Units (SI units) will be used throughout the EDEN ISS study.

For more information, refer to: <http://www.bipm.org/en/si/>.

Table 2-1: Common SI Units used in this document.

Quantity	Name	Symbol	Variations
Length	metre	m	km, mm, μm
Mass	kilogram	kg	g
Time	second	s	hr, min, sec, day, sol
Force	Newton	N	mN
Power	Watt	W	mW, kW
Temperature	Celsius	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	None
Pressure	Pascal	Pa	kPa
Illumination	lux	lx	None
Volume	litre	l or L	mL
Magnetic field	Gauss	Ga	100 MeV
Plant biologically active radiation	Total photon flux density	TPFD	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$ from 280 – 800 nm

3 Antarctic environment as analogue test site

3.1 Description of Antarctic environment

Typical weather conditions at Neumayer III are provided in Figure 3-1. The presented air temperature and wind speed data were collected using the Air Chemistry Observatory situated in proximity to Neumayer Station III and suggest the mobile test facility will experience minimum temperatures of approximately -50°C in the dark season, and summer temperatures reaching just over 0°C . Due to the approximate two months of darkness (and low sun angles) at Neumayer Station III (end of May to end of July), any plant production facility operating year round must incorporate electrical lighting. Snow accumulation and drifting is another factor that must be addressed by any external Antarctic plant production facility.

Figure 3-1: Neumayer III recorded air temperature and wind speed. Air temperature (A) is provided on an hourly average from Jan 1, 2010 to Dec 31, 2012, whereas wind speed (B) on a one minute logging rate is plotted from Jan 1, 2012 to Dec 31, 2012.

3.2 Neumayer Station III as a space analogue site for testing the EDEN ISS mobile test facility

Justification for Antarctic in-situ plant production at stations operated year-round is anchored in the provision of improved crew nutrition and dietary variation. A compelling and tangible benefit beyond dietary considerations is the use of plant production units as horticultural therapy tools that can help alleviate some of the psychological stressors commonly experienced during isolation. The following outlines the advantages of the Neumayer Station III as a test site for the deployment of the EDEN ISS mobile test facility. Focus will be given to the maturation of the EDEN ISS technological and operational readiness for use on future space exploration missions.

Crew Size: The Neumayer Station III crew size varies with the season. During the summer season a team of approximately 40 to 50 people is maintained at the facility. During the Antarctic winter, a small team of normally nine crew members remains to maintain systems and continue annual science data collection. The size and duration of the overwintering team aligns well with current ISS crew sizes as well as those proposed in Moon/Mars design reference missions.

Crew Dynamics: Typical resupply schedules for an Antarctic station are very similar to current space station resupply schedules. There is a typical 9 month lag between resupply missions to Neumayer Station III, which exposes the crew to strong isolation pressure and the associated psychological responses. Unlike laboratory-based long-duration isolation studies, Antarctic crew members must count on technology to survive as there is no door that can be opened to 'end the simulation' in an emergency. Furthermore, although crew members are provided traditional recreational opportunities, growing plants is an activity where the output of a few interested crew members can be enjoyed by the entire crew. From this perspective, effects on the psychological well-being of the crew can be compared with real long-duration space exploration scenarios, where some members of the crew can enjoy passive psychological benefits provided by the efforts of their crew mates.

Inhospitable Environment and Antarctic Treaty Requirements: The harsh environmental conditions typical of Antarctic research stations can only be found at a select few places on Earth. High winds, heavy snow fall (site dependent), low temperatures and seasonal dark periods lasting several months make this an environment where successful plant production requires advanced controlled environment technologies. The Antarctic continent is not only an extremely cold and arid desert, it is also one of the most protected, and biologically sparse environments on Earth. The Neumayer Station III greenhouse module is a high fidelity testing environment for microbiological experiments aimed at refining planetary protection protocols for long-duration human habitation of extra-terrestrial planetary bodies (e.g. Mars). The Antarctic Treaty and its associated Protocol on Environmental Protection place particular requirements on plant production facilities that provide noteworthy analogy to those required in future space-based systems.

Additionally, the initial deployment of the EDEN ISS mobile test facility at the Neumayer Station III serves as a first step towards greater and greater incorporation of bioregenerative life support systems into Antarctic stations. This provides an opportunity to validate complex integrated systems (e.g. air, water and food interfaces) under conditions relevant to the long-term goal of operating plant production facilities on the ISS and on the surface of the Moon and Mars.

3.3 Polarstern and Neumayer Station III Transport and Crane Limits

The maximum Polarstern crane, transport, Neumayer Station III crane(s) and the elevated platform mass limits are provided in Figure 3-2.

Figure 3-2: Polarstern crane, Neumayer Station III crane, transport and elevated platform mass limits.

4 Overall system requirements

4.1 Support infrastructure requirements

4.1.1 Neumayer Station III

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > Neumayer Station III				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
NM-10	AWI	Neumayer Station III shall provide to the EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility (MTF) continuous electrical power supply with maximum 30 kW at 230 VAC, three-phase, 50 Hz.	<p>MTF needs continuous power for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - environmental control system including fans, heaters, humidifiers, dehumidifiers - thermal control system - pumps - sensors - lighting - nutrient actuators - computers - video monitoring - safety sensors for fire/smoke detection 	<p>Inspection of power line</p> <p>Test of peak power supply</p>
NM-20	AWI, DLR	Neumayer Station III shall provide both a hardwired fibre optic cable link and a wireless LAN to support 2-way data/video transfer with the MTF with a bandwidth of at least 1 Mbps.	<p>Need to transfer data and video from MTF to Neumayer Station III control center.</p> <p>Primary data link shall be hardwired fibre optic. Wireless LAN shall be used as back-up in case of failure of primary link.</p>	<p>Inspection of link availability</p> <p>Test of bandwidth</p>
NM-30	AWI	Neumayer Station III shall provide > 5 m ² internal floor space for an EDEN ISS console stations (computers, monitors, desk, chair, and cupboard).	Need for remote monitoring of EDEN ISS system/greenhouse parameters, plant growth data, safety alarms etc. by EDEN ISS scientist(s). To be located in part of the NM-III multipurpose laboratory.	Inspection
NM-40	AWI	Neumayer Station III shall provide 2-way satellite communications link via AWI ground station to DLR, Bremen, Germany, for transfer of data and video communications.	Need to transfer EDEN ISS system monitoring parameters, experiment data and video both to DLR and EDEN ISS Remote User Sites. NM-III satellite link has an uplink bandwidth of up to 1 Mbps.	Inspection of link availability

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > Neumayer Station III				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
NM-50	AWI	<p>Neumayer Station III satellite link shall provide a bandwidth for EDEN ISS as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous 2-way link of at least 150 kbps for EDEN ISS system /experiment data telemetry and commanding - 4 hours per day video and audio conference sessions with a bandwidth of at least 250 kbps. 	<p>Require daily access by DLR and end users to monitor EDEN ISS system and experiment parameter status. A minimum of 10 MB camera images per day will be downloaded to the EDEN ISS ECC and provided to the EDEN ISS science team.</p>	<p>Inspection of link availability</p> <p>Test of bandwidth</p>
NM-60	AWI	<p>Neumayer Station III shall provide wetlab facilities for EDEN ISS personnel including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - space for food sample post-processing and associated tools - plant sample drying facilities - space and power for EDEN ISS supplied freezer for storing microbiological samples - freezing of EDEN ISS food samples - analysis equipment (microscope with photo/video camera, chemical reagent facilities etc.) - space for nutrient storage and preparation. 	<p>Stock nutrient solutions shall be prepared in Neumayer Station III by EDEN ISS personnel. Bulk nutrient solutions shall be prepared in MTF. Activities to be conducted in the NM-III multipurpose laboratory.</p>	<p>Inspection</p>
NM-70	AWI	<p>Neumayer Station III shall provide an internal safe storage container facility for 150 kg of chemicals throughout the EDEN ISS operational phase.</p>	<p>Nutrient salts, acids, bases and disinfection chemicals need to be stored and some handled as dangerous goods. Estimated 70 kg of nutrient salts.</p>	<p>Inspection</p>
NM-80	AWI	<p>Neumayer Station III shall provide back-up scientist trained to monitor and operate EDEN ISS facility; the back-up scientist shall be available throughout the EDEN ISS operational phase.</p>	<p>Non-EDEN ISS scientist needed in case of non-availability of dedicated EDEN ISS scientist (e.g. illness).</p>	<p>Inspection</p>
NM-90	AWI	<p>Neumayer Station III shall provide up to two 20 ft external storage containers.</p>	<p>Storage container(s) needed by EDEN ISS for storing spares, supplies etc. Items</p>	<p>Inspection</p>

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > Neumayer Station III				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
			to be stored may be cooled to -50°C.	
NM-100	AWI	Neumayer Station III shall provide visiting personnel access to Skidoos for transport of material to and from the external storage container and in instances transport of material to and from the Neumayer Station III to the MTF.	The external storage container(s) may be positioned at some distance (approx. 7 to 8 km) from the station/MTF.	Inspection Test of load carrying capabilities
NM-110	AWI	Neumayer Station III shall provide up to 400 L/week of potable water for EDEN ISS.	Needed for water and nutrient feed in MTF. Source: CDR, EDEN ISS-DLR-Overall MTF Design Document-v0.4, Table 6. Start phase may require up to 800 L/week.	Inspection of supply infrastructure
NM-120	AWI	Neumayer Station III shall provide facilities for storage/disposal of all waste from MTF. Waste shall include the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - waste water - inedible biomass - packaging (seeds, nutrient salt containers, etc.) - failed components - cleaning wipes, laboratory gloves, other laboratory analysis consumables e.g. for food quality & safety analysis. 	All waste generated by EDEN ISS has to be processed via the Neumayer Station III and disposed according to the Antarctic Treaty (Madrid 1991) [AD1].	Inspection
NM-130	AWI	20 kg/month of MTF solid waste shall be processed by the existing Neumayer Station III waste handling/protocols. This shall include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sorting - stabilization/storage - labelling - reporting - shipment off the Antarctic continent. 	This waste includes, paper towels, laboratory gloves, disposable pipettes, non-repairable hardware, batteries, etc.	Demonstrate adherence to protocols during test campaign in Bremen
NM-140	AWI	2.5 kg/week of MTF waste biomass shall be processed by the existing Neumayer Station III waste handling/protocols. This	Source: CDR, EDEN ISS-DLR-Overall MTF Design Document-v0.4, Table 6 but estimates include average	Inspection

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > Neumayer Station III				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		shall include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - packaging of the waste - cold storage - shipment off the Antarctic continent. 	harvest results from AIT phase in which ca. 7 kg/week of biomass was harvested from the facility.	
NM-150	AWI	Neumayer Station III nominal waste stream shall support the processing and safe disposal of up to 340 L/week (worst case) of waste nutrient solutions from the EDEN ISS associated activities.	CE-Study: 340 L/week includes 83.3 L/week nutrient solution, 250 L/week cleaning water and 5 L/week germination water. Nutrient solutions need to be replaced after some weeks because of non-suitable ionic balance. Waste solutions sledged/hand-carried in sealed containers to Neumayer Station III.	Demonstrate adherence to protocols during test campaign in Bremen
NM-160	AWI	Polarstern and Neumayer Station III shall provide crane lifting capability to support hoisting of the following EDEN ISS structural facilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobile Test Facility of up to 10000 kg per each 20 ft container (dry mass) - Elevated platform of up to 10000 kg - EDEN ISS external storage container of up to 10000 kg. 	Reference Figure 3-2 for a summary of Polarstern and Neumayer III crane lifting capacities.	Inspection
NM-170	AWI	Neumayer Station III shall provide an Elevated Platform for mounting the MTF containers.	Elevated Platform required for avoiding snow accumulation at ground level. Detailed requirements for Elevated Platform in section 4.1.4.	Inspection
NM-180	AWI, DLR	Neumayer Station III shall provide an outfitted utility sledge for transport of MTF supplies.	Sledge needed for transport of water, CO ₂ bottles, waste etc. Outfitted to handle MTF consumable and waste transport tanks. Sledge provided by AWI. DLR provides installed hardware.	Inspection
NM-190	AWI, DLR	An acoustic alarm shall be sounded in the Neumayer Station III if there is smoke/fire in	Need dedicated hard-wired connection between MTF smoke sensor and Neu-	Inspection, Test

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > Neumayer Station III				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		the MTF or CO ₂ and O ₂ levels exceed pre-defined limits.	mayer Station III.	
NM-200	AWI, DLR	The MTF smoke detection system shall be connected to the overall Neumayer Station III fire alarm system by a dedicated cable.	Need hard-wired link between MTF and Neumayer Station III for maximum reliability and to provide an in-station status of the smoke/fire alarm system.	Inspection, Test
NM-210	AWI	A fixed guiding line shall be established between the MTF and the Neumayer Station III.	In case of blizzard white-out, the line provides safety route for personnel.	Inspection

4.1.2 DLR control center

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > DLR control center				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
DLR-10	DLR	A dedicated EDEN ISS Control Center (ECC) shall be established at DLR, Bremen, Germany. It shall be permanently accessible to authorized personnel.	24/7 operations not planned. But facility needs to be available as required at all times.	Inspection
DLR-20	DLR	The ECC shall include as a minimum: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2x monitor dedicated to MTF systems data display and issuing system commands - 1x monitor dedicated to MTF experiment data display and issuing experiment commands - 1x monitor dedicated to video streaming. - video conferencing application - access to downloaded MTF data and capability to visualize data - telephone with pre-programmed telephone numbers of appropriate EDEN ISS scientists and hardware/software engineers. 		Inspection
DLR-30	DLR	A back-up ECC with a single monitor shall be provided in a		Inspection

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > DLR control center				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		separate facility at DLR, Bremen, in case of main ECC outage.		
DLR-40	DLR	The ECC shall have a 2-way secure Internet based communications link to the AWI ground station for receiving satellite data/video stream from the MTF and for sending commands/video stream to the Neumayer Station III / MTF. The bandwidth shall be up to 1 Mbps.	Maximum data transfer rate is determined by satellite link.	Inspection Test bandwidth
DLR-50	DLR	The ECC shall have 2-way secure Internet based communications link to the remote end user facilities to provide EDEN ISS experiment data and video streaming. The bandwidth shall be up to 1 Mbps.	Maximum data transfer rate is determined by satellite link.	Inspection Test bandwidth

4.1.3 EDEN ISS User Home Bases

An EDEN ISS User Home Base is any remote site that has the possibility to monitor telemetry and issue a limited subset of commands to the MTF for the following:

- MTF hardware systems e.g. ISPR, environmental control system
- execute/modify MTF system software applications
- monitor and modify plant growth experiment control parameters and applicable software applications.

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > EDEN User Home Base				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
EUS-10	TPZ, TASI, UoG, DLO	EDEN ISS User Home Base shall provide dedicated experiment command and monitoring console station.	EDEN ISS User Home Base needs to monitor experiment status (including video monitoring) and issue dedicated experiment control commands.	Inspection
EUS-20	TPZ, TASI, UoG, DLO	EDEN ISS User Home Base shall provide together with DLR a dedicated secure 2-way communications and data transfer link.	EDEN ISS User Home Base needs a secure 2-way link to DLR control center to monitor experiment status (including video monitoring) and issue dedicated experiment control commands.	Inspection
EUS-	TPZ, TASI-	EDEN ISS User Home Base dedi-	Maximum data transfer rate	Inspection

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > EDEN User Home Base				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
30	I, UoG, DLO	cated secure 2-way link with DLR control center shall support a data transfer rate of up to 1 Mbps.	is determined by satellite link.	Test data rate
EUS-40	TPZ, TAS-I, UoG, DLO	EDEN ISS User Home Base shall have the capability to execute a limited set of experiment commands via the ECC. This command subset shall be software authorized by EDEN ISS on-site scientist prior to execution in MTF.	Need to assure the EDEN ISS on-site scientist is aware of and authorizes all commands issued to MTF.	Demonstration during test campaign in Bremen
EUS-50	TPZ, TAS-I, UoG, DLO	The EDEN User Home Base facilities shall support the EDEN ISS Outreach Program by providing on-site support to joint experiments for schools and university students.		N/A, Demonstration?

4.1.4 Elevated platform

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > Elevated platform				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
EP-10	AWI	The Elevated Platform (EP) shall have the following structural characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - platform dimensions 16.12 m long, 4.038 m wide. - platform mounted on 4x struts at an elevation of a maximum of 2.5 m above the snow level (struts are nominally approximately 3.4 m long) - 1 set of inclined stairs with guard rails both sides for access from ground to platform deck - platform enclosed by safety rail. 	Re-build of Air Chemistry Laboratory platform. Platform dimensions and height above ground as defined in Zoth drawing number 07311501, Hubplattform für 2x 20-Fuß-Container Sep 17, 2007.	Inspection
EP-20	AWI	The EP shall be constructed such that it can be disassembled for storage and transport.		Inspection

Overall Requirements > Support infrastructure requirements > Elevated platform				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
EP-30	AWI	The EP platform shall have attachment points for crane hoisting operations.		Inspection
EP-40	AWI	The individual parts of the EP platform shall not exceed 10000 kg in mass.	The combined platform weight can exceed 10000 kg, but separate parts should be below this limit value. Maximum lifting capacity of crane at Neumayer Station III is 10000 kg.	Inspection
EP-50	AWI	The EP shall be able to support up to 48000 kg loading.	Confirmed within the "KSF Statische Berechnung" June 11, 2015. Static analysis assumes total load of both containers together including all contents is assumed to be 48000 kg.	Inspection of "KSF Statische Berechnung" analysis.
EP-60	AWI	The EP structure shall be able to tolerate an annual external ambient temperature range of -55 to +15°C without incurring structural damage.		Inspection of design documentation
EP-70	AWI	The EP surface paint coating shall be silver in color and resistant to salt corrosion, ice crystal erosion during storm and UV (for up to 5 years).		Inspection of design documentation

4.2 Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements

4.2.1 Structural/mechanical and external environment requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Structural/mechanical and external environment requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ME-10	DLR	The MTF shall be housed in two (2) 20 ft high-cube containers mounted end-to-end. The containers shall have corrugated wall profile.	High-cube containers needed to assure ship transport requirements and ground handling capabilities at Neumayer Station III. Use of corrugated profile reduces internal width by 2 x 25 mm.	Inspection
ME-	DLR	The high-cube containers shall	CSC approval needed for	Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Structural/mechanical and external environment requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
20		fulfill Container Safety Convention (CSC) certification requirements.	ship and inner European transport.	(Tested by container manufacturer)
ME-30	DLR	The total mass of each container excluding loose contents and consumables shall not exceed 10000 kg.	Container mass shall not exceed maximum crane handling capabilities of 10000 kg. Reference Figure 3-2.	Inspection
ME-40	DLR	The total mass of the final integrated MTF (both containers) including all installed systems shall not exceed 48000 kg.	MTF mass shall not exceed the maximum elevated platform structural mass limit of 48000 kg. Reference Figure 3-2.	Inspection
ME-50	DLR	The raised floor shall be elevated 30 cm from the standard container floor.	Need under-floor space for fluid lines.	Inspection
ME-60	DLR	The sub-floor area shall have a free space height of at least 25 cm.	The thickness of the structural profiles, and floor panels, can be a maximum of 5 cm.	Inspection
ME-70	DLR	The under-floor space shall be sealed such that liquid spills/leaks are contained within the MTF.	Need to prevent fluids leaking into the MTF interior insulation or externally into the Antarctic environment. CE-Study: MTF design to include drainage sump and pumps to remove collected water or fluid spills and transfer to waste tank.	Test
ME-80	DLR	The built-in floor shall have a loading capability of 300-500 kg/m ² .	DIN 1055-3.	Test
ME-90	AWI	The containers shall be mounted near the Neumayer Station III at a height of ca. 2.5 m above ground on the Elevated Platform.	Elevated mounting needed to reduce snow accumulation around MTF and hence work load for snow clearance.	Inspection
ME-100	DLR	The combined MTF and elevated platform shall be constructed to tolerate a maximum continuous wind speed of 50 m/s from any geographical direction.	The static analysis for the combined MTF plus Elevated Platform, "KSF Statische Berechnung" June 11, 2015, assumes wind speed of 50 m/s.	Inspection of "KSF Statische Berechnung" analysis.
ME-110	AWI	The MTF shall be set-up approximately 400 m south of the Neumayer Station III with the	Minimum distance needed to avoid wind turbulence and snow accumulation both	Inspection, N/A

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Structural/mechanical and external environment requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		longitudinal axis oriented approximately west-east.	at Neumayer Station III and MTF.	
ME-120	DLR	The Cold Porch access door shall be positioned such that it faces the minimum seasonal wind speed direction (approximately west).	Needed for ease of opening and reduction of snow and cold air entry into Cold Porch. Primary wind direction at Neumayer Station III is from the east.	Inspection, N/A
ME-130	DLR	The MTF structure shall be able to tolerate an external ambient temperature range of -55 to +40°C without incurring structural damage.	Upper limit on the temperature range TBC. MTF structure shall withstand high temperatures during testing in Europe and during transport, when crossing the equator.	Inspection of design documentation
ME-140	DLR	The MTF Cold Porch and emergency exit doors shall operate without deformation problems for an external temperature range of -55 to +15° C plus chill factor for a maximum wind speed of 50 m/s.	Both doors need to remain fully operational in all weather conditions in the Antarctic, and during testing.	Inspection of design documentation
ME-150	DLR	The MTF Cold Porch and emergency exit doors shall both be fully sealed against wind and snow access when closed.	Ship external door requirements.	Inspection of design documentation Proven design.
ME-160	DLR	The MTF containers shall be internally insulated such that the overall thermal transmittance U-value is less than 0.3 – 0.35 W/m ² K.	According to EDEN ISS-AS-WP3.3-D3.7b-Thermal Design Document-v0.1, the overall thermal transmittance value is assumed to be 0.3 W/ m ² K for the containers.	Analysis
ME-170	DLR	The internal wall and ceiling insulation cladding shall have a resistance to fixtures of 4000 N pull-out strength.	Requirement applies to a 10 mm thickness TRESPA plate.	Analysis, Test
ME-180	DLR	The internal surfaces of the insulation cladding shall be made of washable material.	Needed for decontaminating surfaces of bacterial and fungal growth.	Inspection, Demonstration
ME-190	DLR	The external MTF surfaces shall be white (RAL 9010) and the paint coating shall be resistant to salt, ice crystal abrasion and	Potential salt spray corrosion due to Neumayer Station III geographical position. Ice crystal abrasion during	Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Structural/mechanical and external environment requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		UV for > 5 years of Antarctic operations.	storm. UV damage during Antarctic spring and summer.	
ME-200	DLR	The MTF shall provide weather sealed access ports for a power cable from the Neumayer Station III, as well as power, data from the interior to the exterior of the MTF.	Power connection made on inside of MTF; located in the SS. Data and power cable interface located in SS.	Inspection
ME-210	DLR	A vertical ladder shall be attached to the outside of the MTF to allow for personnel access to the MTF roof.	Access needed for installation/maintenance of equipment on MTF roof.	Inspection
ME-220	DLR	A small safety rail shall be provided along the longitudinal access of the MTF to allow personnel working on the roof to have a safety fixation point.	Personnel safety.	Inspection
ME-230	DLR	Illumination shall be provided at the exterior of the MTF at the locations described in the container procurement document.		Inspection
ME-240	DLR	The MTF shall provide a weather sealed access port for thermal lines running to the MTF exterior and CO ₂ lines running in to the MTF.	Interface will be positioned in SS.	
ME-250	DLR	The joints between the insulation plates within the MTF shall prevent water leaking into the insulation material.	Ensure no bacterial growth inside the insulation.	Inspection
ME-260	DLR	A minimum of 30 cm shall be provided between the containers to allow for mating joints and utility piping/electrical harness connectors.	30 cm required between the floor structures of the SS and FEG containers	Inspection
ME-270	DLR	A WLAN antenna shall be mounted to a pole on the roof of the west-container for data communication to Neumayer Station III.		Inspection
ME-280	DLR	The MTF shall be designed such that all electric related harness shall be channeled via the ceiling and fluid lines via the sub-floor as far as possible.		Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Structural/mechanical and external environment requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ME-290	ADS	The TransMADDS disinfection agent shall not damage the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - plants - human health - MTF hardware 		Inspection of manufacturer data sheets and/or Test
ME-300	ADS	To avoid residual coatings on MTF sensitive hardware from TransMADDS disinfection agent, the following items need to be protected prior to use: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - optical surfaces (e.g.cameras) - sensors - safety systems - Ethernet switches 	LED optical surfaces do not require protection prior to TransMADDS use.	Inspection
ME-310	ADS	The E-Nose shall be trained to detect the following pathogens: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Escherichia coli - Salmonella 	E-Nose has already been trained to detect following cultures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> • <i>Staphylococcus warneri</i> • <i>Aspergillus versicolor</i> • <i>Penicillium expansum</i> • <i>Pseudomonas geniculata</i> • <i>Micrococcus luteus</i> But need to check if these are relevant to EDEN ISS. Source: CDR, EDEN ISS-ADS-WP3.5-CDR E-Nose and TransMADDS-v0.2.	Subsystem: Test
ME-320	DLR	An air intake inlet for the interior Service Section Air Management System shall be mounted on the south side of the west container.	Design of air intake shall consider inlet position with respect to prevailing winds and possible icing problems.	Inspection
ME-330	DLR	An air outlet for the interior Service Section Air Management System shall be mounted on the south side of the Service Section container.	No formal separate outlet for the Service Section Air Management System is deemed to be required and the air brought into the Service Section will leak out of	Requirement not to be verified

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Structural/mechanical and external environment requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
			the facility via inherent leaks within the Service Section (door, Roxtec interface panels etc.).	
ME-340	DLR	A heat rejection unit shall be positioned outside of the MTF to remove excess heat from the interior environment.	Cooling fluid is TYFOXIT FS0	Inspection
ME-350	DLR	The MTF shall provide an interface to mount CO ₂ bottles, and regulation equipment, on the exterior of the container.	2 CO ₂ bottles, each with a capacity of 13L (10 kg CO ₂), shall be mounted and connected to the distribution system.	Inspection

4.2.2 Internal environmental and thermal control system requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Internal environmental and thermal control system requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
EC-10	DLR, ES	The MTF shall be thermally insulated such that the internal temperature of the Service Section and the FEG can be maintained above 5 °C for at least 45 minutes in case of power loss or internal system failure.	Worst case scenario, based on transient failure scenario CFD simulations.	Analysis, Test
EC-20	DLR, ES	The MTF shall include electric wall-mounted emergency heaters such that the internal temperature of the Service Section and FEG can always be maintained above 5 °C, unless there is a critical failure in the electrical system.		Inspection, Test

4.2.3 Electrical power requirements

The detailed power distribution requirements included in the Service Section detailed requirements, 5.2. The following requirements only cover the interface to the Neumayer Station III.

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Electrical power requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
EL-10	DLR	The MTF shall use in the worst case operational scenario a total of 20 kW of electrical	Worst case power scenario needs to be identified and compared with maximum	Analysis, Test

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Electrical power requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		power.	power available from Neumayer Station III. Average use during day time: 13.9 kW. Average use during night time: 6.7 kW.	
EL-20	DLR	The MTF shall provide an electrical power distribution network compatible with the 230V AC, three-phase, 50 Hz supply of the Neumayer Station III.		Inspection, Test
EL-30	DLR	The MTF shall house an uninterruptible power supply that provides up to 1400 W for up to 0.5 hours at 70% load for the following MTF systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - System computers (Argus, LabVIEW, MTF Server PC) - VOIP telephone? - Wireless LAN network - Switch/Router - Dead man sensor - Fire detection - CO₂, O₂ monitoring - Emergency lights. 	Needed in case of main power loss from Neumayer Station III. Time out for switch-over Neumayer Station III generators is normally in region of seconds.	Inspection

4.2.4 Communications and data handling requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Communications and data handling requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
CDH-10	TPZ	The MTF shall provide both a hard-wired fiber optic cable and a backup wireless LAN connection to support 2-way data transfer with Neumayer Station III with a bandwidth of >1 Mbps.	Need to transfer data and video from MTF to Neumayer Station III control center. Hard-wired fiber optic cable is primary data link. WLAN is backup in case of failure of optical cable link. WLAN shall support more than 100 kbps continuous for science/housekeeping data and up to 300 kbps for video conference (each session up	Inspection of link availability Test of bandwidth

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Communications and data handling requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
			to 2 hours). Patch antennas typically offer considerably more bandwidth.	

4.2.5 Audible noise requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Audible noise requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
AN-10	ADS, AS, CNR, DLO, HS, TPZ, UoG,	<p>The acoustic emissions generated by each MTF audible noise source shall not exceed in any octave band center frequency between 63 Hz and 8000 Hz at a distance of 0.61 m the following limits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 63 Hz 64 dB - 125 Hz 56 dB - 250 Hz 50 dB - 500 Hz 45 dB - 1000 Hz 41 dB - 2000 Hz 39 dB - 4000 Hz 38 dB - 8000 Hz 37 dB. 	<p>NC-40 requirements. Sustained exposure to excessive audible noise is health risk for visiting personnel. CE Study: TransMADDS compressor may violate requirement. But no personnel in impacted MTF section during TransMADDS operation.</p>	Test

4.2.6 Software requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Software requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
SW-10	DLR, TPZ	<p>The following system software applications shall be made available to the MTF system monitor, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor, the ECC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hikvision Camera Client (iVMS) - Hikvision Camera Tool (SADP) - Argus Client - Argus Controls QuickSupport Client - Argus Real Time Window - TightVNC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up and control of the HD cameras • Visualisation of the camera pictures • Access to the Argus control system for changing and monitoring parameters of the MTF • Client used for Argus support tasks • Used for saving most important system sensor and actuator data in data file • Remote control of server PCs • Remote control of 	Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Software requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remote Desktop - FTP Server - TPZ Python Scripts - Heliospectra Software - VPN Client. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> server PCs • Storage area for data logs and pictures • Software for data log and picture acquisition and transfer • Set up software for LED lamps • Etc. 	
SW-20	TAS-I, TPZ	<p>The following EDEN ISS ISPR software applications shall be made available to the MTF system monitor, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor, the ECC and applicable EDEN ISS User Home Bases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RUCOLA (ISPR) Client - TightVNC - Remote Desktop - TPZ Python Scripts - Heliospectra Software - VPN Client. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to the ISPR control system for changing and monitoring parameters of the ISPR • Remote control of server PCs • Remote control of server PCs • Software for data log and picture acquisition and transfer • Set up software for LED lamps • Etc. 	Inspection
SW-30	ADS, AS, CNR, DLO, HS, LIT, TPZ, UoG,	<p>The following plant grow experiment software applications shall be made available to the MTF system monitor, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor, the ECC and applicable EDEN ISS User Home Bases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Winmuster S/W (E-Nose data - commercial S/W) - Argus client - TeamViewer - Image analysis S/W - Chlorophyll concentration - Environmental parameters - Thermal /IR/fluorescence video contamination monitoring 	<p>Plant grow experiment software applications are defined in the following document: EDEN ISS - User Segment Requirements Definition and Architecture Description prepared for WP 3.5 – Plant Health Monitoring Published: 22/11/2017</p>	Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Software requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		- Contaminant management S/W -		

4.2.7 General lighting requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > General lighting requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
GL-10	DLR	The MTF shall provide overhead white light illumination in each enclosed section. The illumination level in the MTF depends on the position within the facility. The illumination shall be sufficient for operations such as examining dials or panels, reading procedures, recording notes etc.	As a guideline the illumination intensity shall be > 200 lux at floor level.	Inspection, Demonstration
GL-20	DLR	Each of the overhead lights shall be manually controlled by 2-way manual switch positioned on the wall next to each door.		Demonstration

4.2.8 Waste management requirements

The EDEN ISS project shall implement a policy to reduce all waste to the minimum possible.

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Waste management requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
WM-10	DLR, AWI	All MTF solid waste shall be stored in sealed containers/bags and removed to the Neumayer Station III for controlled disposal or removal from the Antarctic.		Inspection
WM-20	DLR, AWI	All MTF liquid waste shall be stored in sealed tanks and removed to the Neumayer Station III in sealed container for controlled disposal.		Inspection
WM-30	DLR, AWI	All FEG plant waste shall be stored in sealed contain-		Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Waste management requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		ers/bags and removed to the Neumayer Station III for controlled disposal.		
WM-40	DLR	A log record shall be maintained of the amount of waste-water and solid waste produced by the MTF.	Reference: Umwelt Bundesamt (UBA) letter providing approval for EDEN ISS plant growth experiment in Antarctica.	Inspection
WM-50	DLR, AWI	MTF waste-water and solid waste disposal shall be integrated into the NM-III waste management plan.	Reference: Umwelt Bundesamt (UBA) letter providing approval for EDEN ISS plant growth experiment in Antarctica.	Inspection

4.2.9 External stowage requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > External stowage requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ES-10	AWI	An external stowage container approximately 7-8 km from the Neumayer Station III shall be used for storing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gas bottles (CO₂) - spares - consumables. 		Inspection
ES-20	CNR, DLO, DLR, UoG, TAS-I	Items stored in the external stowage container shall be able to withstand a -50 °C to +10 °C temperature range.		Analysis, Test

4.2.10 Transport requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Transport requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
T-10	DLR, TAS-I	The MTF interiors shall be cleaned and sanitized prior to shipment.		N/A, Inspection
T-20	DLR, TAS-I	All loose items shall be stored safely in containers and/or draws prior to shipment.	In particular sensitive scientific instrument and utensils need to be carefully packed to avoid transport damage.	Inspection
T-30	TAS-I	The ISPR and support equipment shall be in sealed containers when transported from manufacturer to MTF		Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Transport requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		integrator.		
T-40	TAS-I	The ISPR and support equipment shall be housed in the MTF Service Section Container for transport by ship to Antarctic.		Inspection
T-50	DLR	During ship transport the MTF shall be designed to be water tight and tolerate the following ambient parameters: Temperature range -20°C to +40°C Relative Humidity maximum 100%.	The MTF containers need to be sealed for transport on open deck if no place available in ship hold. Since containers not connected during transport need to assure open container walls are weather sealed. Main concern is salt-water ingress inside containers.	Inspection

4.2.11 Maintenance and spares requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Maintenance and spares requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
MS-10	All	A Maintenance and Spares policy shall be established by the EDEN ISS project to include the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - identification of life-limited items - identification of number of critical spares needed - storage requirements for all spares - identification of storage place for all spares 		Inspection
MS-20	All	The Maintenance and Spares policy shall be applicable to all EDEN ISS hardware.		N/A, Inspection
MS-30	All	Hardware developers shall provide a list of all life-limited items and define number of spares required for critical		Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Maintenance and spares requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		items.		
MS-40	CNR, DLO, DLR, TAS-I, UoG	Sufficient chemicals shall be available to support complete restart of plant growth experiments in the FEG.	In case of plant growth failure caused by chemical/biological contamination and need to restart FEG operations.	Inspection
MS-50	CNR, DLO, DLR, TAS-I, UoG	Sufficient chemicals shall be available to support 1.5 years of continuous plant grow experiments.		Inspection
MS-60	DLR	The MTF interior surfaces shall be cleaned at least every 2 months using either isopropyl alcohol or 10% bleach. Floors should be cleaned weekly. Tables should be cleaned at the end of each working day.	Regular cleaning needed to avoid introduction of fungal/ bacterial contamination. Highly suggested Antarctic cleaning agents. Many documents including past Antarctic system as well as: Australia and France ATCM XXXV - CEP XV - WPO25_Guidelines to Min Non-Native – Hydroponics. Reference MTF hygiene protocol.	Inspection

4.2.12 Safety requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Safety requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
S-10	AS, DLR, TPZ	A Safety Training Manual shall be provided by the EDEN ISS project describing conduct of operations by MTF visiting personnel. The Safety Training Manual shall include procedures detailing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - how to use personal alarm devices - which requirements to fulfill prior to going to MTF e.g. verbal announcement to other person(s) - what to do in case of chemical spills (both 		Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Safety requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		personal injury and environmental impacts) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fire drill including fire extinguisher positions, emergency exit route(s) - emergency procedures and fire simulation test frequency - environment sensor test frequency e.g. smoke detectors. 		
S-20	DLR	Visiting MTF personnel shall provide written confirmation that they have read and understood the EDEN ISS Safety Training Manual prior to first visit.		Inspection
S-30	DLR	Visiting MTF personnel shall record name (block text plus signature), time of entry and departure in a log-book in the MTF.	Data to be used to control crew time and as input to EDEN ISS psychological studies.	Inspection
S-40	DLR, AWI	Safety rails shall be provided enclosing the following elements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Platform - Access stairs to platform (both sides). 	Risk of personnel falling.	Inspection
S-50	DLR	The environmental control system shall provide a Fire Detection System through-out the MTF that is integrated with the overall MTF caution and warning system.	Need to monitor for fire in FEG (both center aisle and plant growth units), Service Section and Cold Porch.	Inspection
S-60	DLR	Smoke detectors and O ₂ /CO ₂ safety detectors shall be mounted within each enclosed space of the MTF.	Cold porch, Service Section and FEG. An independent CO ₂ monitoring system for personnel safety shall be implemented (i.e. in addition to the nominal AMS CO ₂ monitoring system).	Inspection
S-70	DLR	Smoke detectors and CO ₂ /O ₂ safety detectors shall have backup battery power in case of main power failure and shall be tested every 1 month to		Inspection, Demonstration

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Safety requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		assure function.		
S-80	AS, TPZ	Smoke detectors and O ₂ /CO ₂ safety detectors shall be monitored such that an acoustic alarm is sounded on all EDEN ISS system consoles in case of smoke/fire, and critical CO ₂ level.	Remote detection of smoke/fire in MTF needed when no personnel present.	Demonstration
S-90	DLR	Internal emergency exit route shall be clearly marked on MTF floor and over all relevant doors.		Inspection
S-100	DLR	External emergency exit route shall be indicated both on MTF and Platform.		Inspection
S-110	AS	Fire extinguishers shall be provided in each of the following sections of the MTF: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cold Porch - Service Section - FEG. 		Inspection
S-120	DLR	All chemical handling by personnel shall only be performed with gloves, lab coat and eye protection both in NM-III multipurpose laboratory and in MTF.		N/A, Inspection
S-130	DLR	All chemicals brought to or removed from the MTF shall be transported in sealed containers.		N/A, Inspection
S-140	AWI, DLR	In case of a chemical spill during transport between MTF and Neumayer Station III, standard station procedures to be immediately initiated for clean-up operations.		N/A, Demonstration
S-150	AWI, DLR	A chemical spill kit shall be available to the EDEN ISS personnel in the MTF.	Kit for cleaning-up chemical spills shall be defined in Safety Training Manual. Instructions for using kit shall be defined in Safety Training Manual.	Inspection
S-160	AWI, DLR	Minor chemical spills shall be immediately cleaned by visit-		N/A, Demonstration

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Safety requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		ing personnel and cleaning materials stored in sealed container for transport to Neumayer Station III.		stration
S-170	AWI, DLR	Major chemical spills shall be immediately reported to Neumayer Station III and dedicated procedure initiated for clean-up operations.		N/A, Demonstration
S-180	DLR	Visiting personnel shall always wear protective glasses when entering and working in the MTF FEG.	Potential eyesight damage from small amount of UV-wavelength emitted from LEDs. Glasses not required when plant lighting powered off.	N/A, Demonstration
S-190	DLR	All electrical power points and plugs in the MTF shall as a minimum meet the European CE standard.	Covered plugs needed.	Inspection
S-200	DLR	Personnel shall assure there is drinking water available in the MTF at all times.	Needed to avoid personnel dehydration when working for extended periods in MTF.	Inspection, Demonstration
S-210	DLR	An emergency first-aid kit shall be provided in the MTF.		Inspection
S-220	DLR	The first-aid kit shall be clearly marked and placed in an easily accessible position (or multiple positions) in the MTF.		Inspection, Demonstration
S-230	AS, DLR	In case of MTF power and/or lighting system failure, a hand lamp/torch shall be available on an easily accessible and visible wall mounting in both the Service Section and the FEG.	Hand lamp shall illuminate automatically from own battery if power or lights fail so as to be visible to visiting personnel.	Inspection
S-240	DLR	A set of climate protection clothing shall be available in the FEG in case of emergency exit from MTF.	As a result of the EDEN ISS setup at NM-III it has been decided that there shall be no climate protection clothing provided in the FEG due to lack of storage volume near the emergency exit door. In worst case personnel can run the 400 m to the station. Although there are obviously	Requirement not to be verified

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Safety requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
			some extreme exceptions, personnel will have access to clothes in the cold porch. If there is a really bad emergency that personnel have to get out of the FEG emergency exit door than it is highly likely that they would not have time to grab much in the way of clothing. But considering the station is only 400 m away – this is still a survivable distance even in some of the worst outside conditions. (plus it could still be possible to run around to the other side of the MTF to grab clothing).	
S-250	DLR	A dedicated eye wash station shall be included in the SS.	Minimum requirement should be disposable emergency eye wash bottles.	Inspection
S-260	DLR	The smoke, CO ₂ and O ₂ safety detectors shall implement an acoustic and visual caution and warning system for alerting personnel when ambient monitored parameters exceed concentration limits or in case of fire detection.	The acoustic and visual warning system shall be deployed in both the MTF and NM-III. In addition, the caution and warning telemetry shall be displayed on MTF monitor in Service Section and on Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor.	Inspection, Demonstration
S-270	DLR	Emergency portable lights shall be available in each section of the MTF. Each light shall be powered by a rechargeable battery pack.	Needed in case of loss of power from Neumayer Station III.	Inspection
S-280	DLR	Fire extinguishers shall be provided in the FEG, Service Section and Cold Porch. Each fire extinguisher shall be positioned in a readily accessible position and kept free from obstacles at all times.		Inspection

4.2.13 Antarctic treaty compatibility requirements

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Antarctic treaty compatibility requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Antarctic treaty compatibility requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ANT - 10	DLR, DLO	The EDEN ISS project shall only use sanitized seeds as basis for plant growth investigations.	No germinated seeds shall be imported into MTF with the exception of the strawberry seedlings transported to Antarctica.	N/A, Inspection
ANT - 20	DLR	All hardware used in the MTF shall be sterilized prior to use.	The MTF environment (in particular the FEG) with high humidity/temperature ideal place for growth of fungi, bacteria etc.	Inspection
ANT - 30	DLR, AWI	Waste liquids from the FEG shall be stored in a dedicated sealed tank in the MTF Service Section container and shall be removed to the Neumayer Station III for controlled disposal or shipment out of Antarctica in sealed containers.	No waste liquids shall be released into the Antarctic environment. Protocol on Environmental Protection, Annex III – Article VI.	Inspection
ANT - 40	DLR, AWI	All plant waste shall be stored in sealed containers and removed to the Neumayer Station III for controlled disposal.	Protocol on Environmental Protection, Annex III – Article VI.	Inspection
ANT- 50	DLO, DLR	Only food crops will be grown within the MTF.	Protocol on Environmental Protection, Annex II.	Inspection
ANT- 60	All	The MTF shall not use soil.	Protocol on Environmental Protection, Annex II - Appendix C.	Inspection
ANT- 70	DLO, DLR	No pesticides shall be used as part of the EDEN ISS project.	Protocol on Environmental Protection, Annex III – Article VII.	Inspection
ANT- 80	All	Polystyrene beads, chips or similar forms of packaging shall not be employed for the shipment of EDEN ISS project hardware to Neumayer Station III.	Protocol on Environmental Protection, Annex III – Article VII.	Inspection
ANT- 90	All	The use of PVC is strongly discouraged and every effort shall be made to avoid employing this material.	Protocol on Environmental Protection, Annex III – Article VII.	N/A Requirement to be treated as guideline.
ANT- 100	DLR	All persons accessing the hydroponics facility should have clean hands, footwear and clothing. Handling of fresh,	Australia and France ATCM XXXV - CEP XV - WP025_Guidelines to Min Non-Native - Hydroponics.	N/A Requirement to be imple-

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Antarctic treaty compatibility requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		imported produce prior to entering the facility should be avoided.		mented in Safety Training Manual.
ANT-110	DLR	No food shall be taken into the FEG section of the MTF.	Australia and France_ATCM XXXV - CEP XV - WP025_Guidelines to Min Non-Native – Hydroponics. Reference MTF hygiene protocol.	N/A Requirement to be implemented in Safety Training Manual.
ANT-120	DLR	Smokers shall not enter the Service Section or FEG unless they have washed their hands and replaced their clothing.	Tobacco can carry the mosaic virus.	N/A Requirement to be implemented in Safety Training Manual.
ANT-130	DLR	Invertebrate traps (sticky traps) shall be installed in the MTF and monitored regularly.	Various Antarctic hydroponic guidelines and as a result of past non-native species issues with past Antarctic facilities.	Inspection
ANT-140	DLR	Sealed transport cases shall be used for the transport of harvested plant material from the MTF to the NM-III station.	Biological samples shall be collected, stored and stabilized in accordance with tight procedures, as exposure to unfavourable external conditions of only a few minutes can alter their characteristics and jeopardize results. E.g. transfer of food vegetables from the MTF to NM-III shall be protected from freezing with appropriate containers.	Inspection
ANT-150	DLR	Non-fruit bearing plants such as herbs shall not be allowed to flower and go to seed.	Australia and France_ATCM XXXV - CEP XV - WP025_Guidelines to Min Non-Native - Hydroponics	Inspection
ANT-160	DLR	In case of inadvertent flowering of non-fruit bearing plants, the flowers shall be removed and incinerated, autoclaved and/or sealed appropriately for removal from Antarctica.	Australia and France_ATCM XXXV - CEP XV - WP025_Guidelines to Min Non-Native - Hydroponics	Inspection

Overall Requirements > Mobile Test Facility overall system requirements > Antarctic treaty compatibility requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ANT-170	DLR	All plant seeds transported to the Antarctic for the EDEN IS project shall be logged and a record maintained of approximate quantity and use when removed from seed containers.	Removed seeds do not have to be recorded on a seed by seed basis. But approximate quantity shall be recorded in a checklist in the seed container.	Inspection
ANT-180	DLR	All plants produced in the MTF that are destined for human consumption must be consumed within the NM-III environs.	Requirement needed to prevent cross-contamination between Antarctic stations. Requirement shall also apply to visiting personnel from other stations prohibiting import of plant material into NM-III environs.	Inspection

5 Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements

5.1 Cold Porch detailed requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Cold Porch detailed requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
AL-10	DLR	The Cold Porch shall have an access door for visiting personnel that can be manually operated from both sides.		Inspection, Demonstration
AL-20	DLR	The Cold Porch door shall have a window dimensions 40*40 cm.	Allows visiting personnel to visually control inside of Cold Porch prior to entry or outside when exiting.	Inspection
AL-30	DLR	The Cold Porch shall have an internal manually operated door that connects to the Service Section.		Inspection, Demonstration
AL-40	DLR	The Cold Porch shall have a minimum floor area of 3.225 m ² .	Need enough space for visiting personnel to change from external thermal protection clothing to laboratory clothing.	Inspection
AL-50	DLR/LSG	The Cold Porch shall provide storage for both external and internal clothing of 3 visiting personnel. Internal clothing shall be stored in a container/locker.		Inspection
AL-60	AS	Cold Porch heaters shall be automatically activated by the environmental control system when ambient temperature falls below 5 °C.		Test
AL-70	TPZ	The Cold Porch shall provide for video monitoring of visiting personnel activities.	Need to assure visiting personnel are healthy and safe.	Inspection
AL-80	DLR	The Cold Porch shall provide at least 1 (one) standard 230 V power outlet.		Inspection
AL-90	DLR	The Cold Porch shall house the fresh air system (Service Section air management system) of the MTF.		

5.2 Service Section detailed requirements

5.2.1 Structural/mechanical and stowage requirements.

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Service Section detailed requirements > Structural/mechanical and stowage requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
SS-1010	DLR	The Service Section shall have a minimum floor area of 9.05 m ² .		Inspection
SS-1020	DLR	The Service Section shall house the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISPR - Air management system (for FEG) - Nutrient delivery system - Power distribution system - Command & data handling system - Thermal control system - Desk, chair, and locker - General storage facility - Sink - Safety equipment 	CE-Study: Fresh and waste water tanks moved from Service Section to Cold Porch sub-floor.	Inspection
SS-1030	DLR	The Service Section shall have a window facing the Neumayer Station III.	Window needed for safety and psychological reasons.	Inspection
SS-1040	DLR	The Service Section shall house a tool-kit containing the general tools required to conduct basic maintenance as well as crop harvest related tools within the MTF.		Inspection
SS-1050	DLR	The Service Section shall house a warm water sink.		Inspection, Demonstration
SS-1060	DLR	The Service Section shall provide storage facilities for consumables.	Need to store consumables such as sampling devices in MTF.	Inspection
SS-1070	DLR	The Service Section shall provide for the disposal of both liquid and solid waste. Liquid waste shall be removed by pipe to the waste tank in the Cold Porch section. Solid waste shall be temporarily stored in sealed containers/bags for removal to Neu-	CE-Study: Waste tank of moved from Service Section to Cold Porch sub-floor.	Inspection

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Service Section detailed requirements > Structural/mechanical and stowage requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		mayer Station III.		

5.2.2 Environmental and thermal requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Service Section detailed requirements > Environmental and thermal requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ET-10	AS, DLR	The environmental control system in the Service Section shall supports the following internal ambient parameter ranges: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal temperature 16 – 27 °C - Relative humidity 25-30%. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature controlled at level required for human comfort. - Relative humidity controlled such that dew point does not lead to condensation on internal surfaces and subsequent risk of microbial and fungal growth. 	Review of Design
ET-20	DLR	The environmental control system shall be designed to exchange air with the external environment.	<p>Needed to avoid dangerous CO₂ and O₂ concentration for visiting personnel or when using cleaning fluids /materials.</p> <p>Fresh air inlet from MTF environment. But no outlet for venting of MTF internal waste air. Assumed there will be enough air exchanged during normal ingress/egress of personnel.</p>	Review of Design
ET-30	DLR	The environmental control system shall provide for heating external air vented into the Service Section.		Inspection
ET-40	DLR	The thermal control system shall provide a minimum of two coolant loops with different characteristics.		Review of Design
ET-50	DLR, ES, TASI	The thermal control system shall provide a coolant loop to the ISPR with the following	CE Study: Parameters are for worst case daylight simulation for plant growth.	Test

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Service Section detailed requirements > Environmental and thermal requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - water and Tyfocor L mixture - supply temperature 16 – 20°C - maximum return temperature 25°C - maximum flow rate 190 kg/hr - flow delta pressure between inlet and outlet quick disconnects shall be 40 kPa 		
ET-60	DLR, ES, HS	The thermal control system shall provide a coolant loop to the MTF air conditioning system with the following characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - water and Tyfocor L mixture - supply temperature 8 °C - maximum return temperature 16°C - maximum flow rate 1082 L/h - Pressure loss 72.9 kPa 	CE Study: Parameters from ES final presentation are for worst case daylight simulation for plant growth.	Test
ET-70	DLR, ES	The thermal control system shall provide a water coolant loop to the FEG LED panels with the following characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - water and Tyfocor L mixture - supply temperature 20 °C - maximum return temperature 25 °C 	CE Study: Parameters from ES final presentation are for worst case daylight simulation for plant growth. Of note include ES modeling estimates of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - maximum flow rate 1.1 m³/hr - pressure loss for one “string” of 2 panels = 8 kPa 	Test
ET-80	DLR, ES	The thermal control system shall provide a coolant loop to an external heat rejection unit with the following characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 100% TYFOXIT F50coolant - supply temperature 	Supply temperature is the return temperature from the plate heat exchangers. Return temperature is the temperature of the fluid after heat rejection to the environment. Selected freecooler has	Review of Design

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Service Section detailed requirements > Environmental and thermal requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		5°C - maximum return temperature 5 °C - maximum flow rate 2.5 m ³ /hr	a flowrate specification of 2.23 m ³ /hr (reference S-GFH 067C/2-U(D)-F6/12P freecooler datasheet). Worst case hot external air temperature is 5°C	
ET-90	DLR, ES	The thermal control system shall provide a heat rejection unit to dissipate 11.0 kW of thermal load from 100% TYFOXIT F50 coolant to the external Antarctic environment		Review of Design, Inspection
ET-100	DLR, ES	The heat rejection unit shall be able to operate in temperatures ranging from -40 to +15°C		Review of Design
ET-110	DLR, ES	The thermal control system shall monitor and control the following parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LED cooling line temperature and pressure - AMS cooling line temperature and pressure - Freecooler cooling line temperature and pressure - ISPR cooling line temperature and pressure - Additional cooling line temperature sensors (8) - Freecooler radiator temperature 		Review of Design
ET-120	DLR	The thermal control system shall provide sufficient volume of Tyfocor-L and TYFOXIT F50 to allow to allow the coolant loop to be refilled at least 3 times during the Antarctic operations phase.		Inspection

5.2.3 Electrical power requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Service Section detailed requirements > Electrical power requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
SS-2010	DLR	The Service Section shall provide a Main Power Box that provides for the distribution of the NM-III supplied 230 VAC into both 230 VAC lines and 24 VDC lines as required by the various MTF subsystems.	See D3.13a – PCD Design Document, Power Control and Distribution and CDH, v0.2, section 1.2. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Required power distribution lines are 9x 230 VAC and 2x 24 VDC. 	Test

5.2.4 Command and data handling requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Service Section detailed requirements > Command and data handling requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
SS-3010	DLR, TPZ, UoG	The Service Section shall provide a computer system and display for monitoring overall MTF system telemetry and issuing commands.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature controlled at level required for human comfort. - Relative humidity controlled such that dew point does not lead to condensation on internal surfaces and subsequent risk of microbial and fungal growth. 	Review of Design
SS-3020	DLR, UoG, TPZ	The Service Section shall provide a computer system for monitoring FEG telemetry data and issuing commands.	<p>Needed to avoid dangerous CO₂ and O₂ concentration for visiting personnel or when using cleaning fluids /materials.</p> <p>Fresh air inlet from MTF environment. But no outlet for venting of MTF internal waste air. Assumed there will be enough air exchanged during normal ingress/egress of personnel.</p>	Review of Design
SS-3030	TAS-I	The Service Section shall provide a computer for commanding and monitoring the EDEN ISS ISPR.		Inspection
SS-	TPZ, DLR	The Service Section shall pro-		Review of

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Service Section detailed requirements > Command and data handling requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
3040		vide video monitoring and video teleconferencing facilities.		Design
SS-3050	ADS, AS, CNR, DLO, HS, TPZ, UoG,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The MTF system-, EDEN ISS ISPR-, and FEG housekeeping data shall be made available to the MTF system monitor, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor, the ECC and applicable EDEN ISS User Home Bases. 	CE Study: Parameters are for worst case daylight simulation for plant growth.	Test
SS-3060	AS, TPZ, DLR, UoG	<p>The following MTF system commands shall be executable from the MTF system monitors in the MTF Service Section, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor and the ECC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All EDEN ISS ISPR and FEG plant growth system control parameters - All FEG plant growth system control parameters. - Service Section environmental control parameters. 	CE Study: Parameters from ES final presentation are for worst case daylight simulation for plant growth.	Test

5.3 ISPR detailed requirements

Note: An objective of the EDEN ISS is to develop an **ISPR-like system** (International Standard Payload Rack) for future testing of a plant growth payload on-board ISS. To reduce the effort for such a future application there are the following options:

1. EDEN ISS ISPR shall fulfill as far as possible the standard ISPR requirements detailed in [RD2]
2. Plan to use the European Drawer Rack 2 (EDR2) as standard ISPR for the EDEN payload.

With the second option the EDEN ISS ISPR design shall concentrate on providing the physical interfaces to the EDEN ISS payload as defined in [RD3].

The following system requirements for the ISPR structure assume that the flight EDEN ISS ISPR shall be housed as a payload in the EDR2 (option 2).

The requirements are established with respect to the ISPR ground demo that will be tested in Antarctica within the scope of the EDEN ISS project. Since the ISPR system shall be a precursor of an ISS flight demonstrator, preliminary indication of additional requirements to be verified in the ISS demonstration phase are also reported in the “Comments” column (to be completed by fully applicable ECSS standards). In general, the additional requirements include more stringent failure detection, human factors, safety, data management control, mechanical and structural IFs, environmental loads (i.e. launch, microgravity, radiation), human time allocation for operation and maintenance, etc.

5.3.1 ISPR system demonstration requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > ISPR system demonstration requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-1010	TAS-I	The EDEN ISS ISPR system shall comprise an ISPR-like rack facility for the growth of consistently safe vegetable food in microgravity.	Food safety and logistics (ordinary and extraordinary maintenance, re-resources/waste management) are key demonstration objectives for the Antarctica campaign. Microgravity compatibility verification is an objective of the future flight demo.	System Level: Review of Design
ISPR-1020	TAS-I	The ISPR shall have dimensions and shape similar to flight EDR2.	No pivots or KBAR required. No curved back plane as required for flight ISPR.	System Level: Review of Design
ISPR-1030	TAS-I	The ISPR shall have internal payload interfaces similar to EDR2 internal payload interfaces.	The ISPR design shall support the effort of redesign toward ISS as far as practicable within the project planned cost constraints.	System Level: Review of Design
ISPR-1040	TAS-I	The ISPR shall house 2 independently controlled plant cultivation modules providing together a total production area of approximately 0.5 - 1 m ² .	One module for taller plants, one for shorter plants. No hard requirement for production area in EDEN ISS ISPR.	System Level: Review of Design

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > ISPR system demonstration requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-1050	TAS-I	The ISPR system shall allow both remote and in situ monitoring and control activities.		System Level: Review of Design, Test

5.3.2 Crop Life support general functional requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Crop Life support general functional requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-2010	TAS-I	<p>The ISPR shall provide an atmospheric environment suitable for the growth of selected crops, controlling in the selected acceptability ranges the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temperature • Relative humidity • Total pressure • O₂ concentration • CO₂ concentration • Trace gases and odors • Microbial load • Airborne particles. 	<p>a. The future flight demo will also provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ionizing radiation control • non- ionizing radiation control <p>b. The acceptability ranges of the identified parameters will be defined upon selection of target crops and indications from the project scientific board.</p>	<p>System Level: Analysis, Test</p> <p>Equipment Level: Analysis, Test</p>
ISPR-2020	TAS-I	<p>The ISPR shall provide means to respond to environmental contingencies, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fire • Contingency atmospheric temperature conditions. 	<p>a. The future flight demo will also provide means to respond to additional environmental contingencies, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • uncontrolled pressure variations • hazardous radiation exposure. 	<p>System Level: Review of Design, Analysis</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis</p>
ISPR-2030	TAS-I	<p>The ISPR shall provide for the selected crop vital resources supply within defined acceptability range and quality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water • Macro and Micro Nutrients • O₂ • CO₂ • Illumination. 	<p>a. The future flight demo will provide the same functions, with the additional constrain of verification in microgravity environment</p> <p>b. The acceptability ranges of the identified parameters will be defined upon selection of target crops and indications from the project scientific</p>	<p>System Level: Review of Design, Test</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis, Test</p>

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Crop Life support general functional requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
			board.	
ISPR-2040	TAS-I	<p>The ISPR shall provide means to manage produced wastes, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depleted growth media • Inedible plant material • Depleted nutrient solution/ waste water • Waste gas (i.e. O₂ rich air). 	<p>a. The flight demo will also assess how to manage produced wastes.</p> <p>b. For the EDEN ISS ISPR, the provided means could simply be crew accessible ports for manual replacement.</p>	<p>System Level: Review of Design</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design</p>
ISPR-2050	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide a system to maintain internal compartments pressure equal to the cabin atmosphere.		<p>System Level: Review of Design</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis, Test</p>

5.3.3 Structural/mechanical, environmental and stowage requirements.

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Structural/mechanical, environmental and stowage requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-3010	TAS-I	The ISPR shall have fixed secondary structure for harness fixation during crane hoisting.	Needed for ship/road transport and assembly in MTF.	<p>System Level: Review of Design</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design</p>
ISPR-3020	TAS-I	The ISPR shall tolerate an ambient temperature range of 16 – 30°C and relative humidity 25 – 70% during normal operations in the MTF.	These range values envelop the Columbus ones (Temp. 18-27 °C; RH 25-70%).	<p>System Level: Review of Design</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design</p>
ISPR-3030	TAS-I	The ISPR shall tolerate ambient temperature range of -10°C to	During transport from ship to MTF in Antarctic.	System Level: Analysis

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Structural/mechanical, environmental and stowage requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		+40°C, relative humidity of 20% to 70% without incurring structural or functional damage during non-operational transport phase.	Bulk of ISPR to be transported installed in MTF. Exact shock g-level of transport over the ice is presently unknown but will be measured as part of project. Design considered that shocks would be present.	Equipment Level: Analysis
ISPR-3040	TAS-I	The ISPR shall be fixed to MTF wall and floor when in operation.	MTF wall/floor loading shall be compliant to maximum weight of ISPR including payload.	System Level: Review of Design, Inspection Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-3050	TAS-I	The ISPR shall have 2 interfaces for mounting external equipment to the racks.	2 during CE Study	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-3060	TAS-I	The ISPR shall have a mass of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - rack primary structure < 150 kg - payload < 450 kg. 	Analogy with EDR2 full rack mass budget.	System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Analysis, Test
ISPR-3070	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide a Utility Interface Panel (UIP) for resource connections similar to what is defined in [RD2], Figure 3.3-5.	No need for ISS flight qualified connectors. Not all standard ISPR UIP resource connectors need to be used in MTF ISPR i.e. need the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main power - waste gas - video sync - LAN-1 - LAN-2 - video - EWACS. 	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-	TAS-I	The ISPR shall use COTS me-	COTS hardware needed	System Level:

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Structural/mechanical, environmental and stowage requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
3080		chanical hardware to the maximum extent possible (i.e. including standard lockers and drawers as foreseen for EDR-2 subsystems).	to reduce costs.	Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-3090	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide a connector interface for provision of CO ₂ to the Growth Chamber Modules via an external gas cylinder.		System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-3100	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide a connector interface for provision of fresh water to the ISPR nutrient delivery system.		System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-3110	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide a connector for sampling of fluid from the ISPR nutrient delivery system.		System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-3120	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide a vent for removal of waste gases to MTF atmosphere. The vented gases shall be filtered by the ISPR to reduce contaminants to a minimum.		System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-3130	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide a serial RS-232 connector interface.	Needed for possible external direct commanding/monitoring of ISPR.	Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design

5.3.4 Electrical interface requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Electrical interface requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-4010	TAS-I	The ISPR shall use < 2 kW electrical power.	Analogy with EDR2 full rack power budget. CE Study determined highest peak load to be 1.5 kW with both Plant Growth Chambers LEDs simultaneously providing 600 $\mu\text{mol/s/m}^2$.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test
ISPR-4020	TAS-I	The ISPR shall use the 230 VAC provided by the Neumayer Station III.	Target EDR 2 uses Columbus 116 – 126 VDC electrical power, but COTS equipment used in the project may benefit from 230 VAC availability. MTF ISPR shall use 24 VDC internally for Growth Plant Chamber LED illumination. 230 VAC to 24 VDC converter to be responsibility of ISPR developer.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-4030	TAS-I	The ISPR 230 VAC to 24 VDC power converter shall comply with the electrical characteristics in [RD3] section 3.2.	24 VDC power supply to ISPR needs to comply with the Columbus standard power supply voltage characteristics.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-4040	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide a 230 VAC to the LED panel Power Supply Unit (PSU). The PSU shall convert to 48 VDC for the LED and CPU. Variable power output to the LED shall be controlled via the CPU.	CDR results: LED panels for plant cultivation illumination shall use 48 VDC. The LEDs shall be dimmable in the range 100 – 600 $\mu\text{mol/s/m}^2$. CE Study determined highest peak load to be 1.5 kW with both Plant Growth Chambers LEDs simultaneously providing 600 $\mu\text{mol/s/m}^2$.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-4050	TAS-I	The ISPR shall have a dedicated panel providing manual switches/display to control the follow-		System Level: Review of Design, Test

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Electrical interface requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		ing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISPR power main switch - 6x single drawer power switches - main telemetry parameters display - illumination and irrigation manual timer override - target temperature override 		Equipment Level: Review of Design. Test

5.3.5 Thermal interface requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Thermal interface requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-5010	TAS-I	The ISPR shall use cooling water supplied by the MTF with a fixed flow rate < 190 kg/h and temperature 16 – 20°C.	Analogy with EDR2 full rack cooling budget	System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Analysis
ISPR-5020	TAS-I	The ISPR shall return coolant water to the MTF environmental control system with a temperature <25°C.	CE Study: ISPR coolant return temperature shall be worst case 25 °C (maximum water inlet temperature, peak power, no dissipation to environment).	System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Analysis
ISPR-5030	TAS-I	The ISPR shall assure that the delta pressure between the inlet and outlet quick disconnects is 40 kPa when ISPR operated at selected flow rate.		System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Analysis

5.3.6 Command and data handling interface requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Command and data handling interface requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-6010	TAS-I	The ISPR shall rely either on LAN or RS232 interfaces for commanding (i.e. loading new programs) and data collection of		System Level: Review of Design

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Command and data handling interface requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		rack functions from the external C&DH system.		Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-6020	TAS-I	The ISPR shall rely on a local data acquisition and command board for the EDEN ISS payload sensors and actuators interaction.	National Instruments Compact Rio is the currently assumed baseline, since it can be upgraded with code commonality to a NI SBRio, keen to flight optimization.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design

5.3.7 Illumination system requirements

For detailed requirements of the illumination system, see 6.4.5. It is foreseen to use the same illumination panel for FEG and for ISPR.

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Lighting requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-7010	HS	The ISPR shall provide an illumination system to the payload cultivation modules comprising the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LED plates - LED plate mounting I/F - LED plate cooling element - LED plate health status monitoring. 		System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test
ISPR-7020	HS	The Plant Growth Chamber shall be illuminated by a single LED panel of maximum dimensions 60 x 40 x 7.5 cm.	CE Study: Need for single panel to provide maximum light distribution in Plant Growth Chambers.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test
ISPR-7030	HS	The LED panel shall be water cooled via a cold-plate.	CE Study: commercial off-the-shelf cold plate.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level:

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Lighting requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
				Review of Design, Test
ISPR-7040	HS	The LED panel shall be dimmable from 100 to 600 $\mu\text{moles/s/m}^2$.	CE Study: Illumination range and spectral characteristics shall be same as LEDs in FEG (see FEG-5030 and FEG-5040)	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test
ISPR-7050	HS	Each LED panel shall be water cooled via the MTF Thermal Control System such that the maximum operating temperature of each does not exceed 40 °C.	CE Study requirement. LED automatic power cut-off when temperature exceeds 50°C.	Test
ISPR-7060	HS	Each LED panel shall have a control / power distribution box that accepts an Ethernet connector and 230 VAC power feed.	CE Study requirement. The LED power controller shall convert from 230 VAC to 48 VDC.	Inspection
ISPR-7070	HS	Each LED panel shall be monitored for the following parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Status (Status) - Set point per panel (S_450, S_660, S_735, S_5700) [2 byte integer] - Temperature per bar in the panel (T1, T2, T3) [2 byte integer] 1/10 degC - Current per bar (I1, I2, I3) [2 byte integer] milliamp - HW configuration HW_config [String] - FW version FW_version [String]. 	CE Study requirement.	Test

5.3.8 Safety requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Safety requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Safety requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-8010	TAS-I	The ISPR shall have a guarded, two-position, manually operated switch installed in a visible and accessible position on the front of each rack that removes all power to the rack during maintenance and handling.	Power disconnected when maintenance switch open. Power only supplied to rack when switch position returned to closed status.	System Level: Review of Design, Inspection, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-8020	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide the capability to control and monitor a smoke Detector, control a red LED smoke indicator, and monitor the fan ventilation status as described in [RD2], 3.3.4.1.	Re-use existing standard ISPR rack smoke detector system as applied to EDR-2.	System Level: Review of Design, Inspection, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-8030	TAS-I	The ISPR shall be constructed from materials that are non-toxic and off gas no dangerous chemicals according to Neumayer Station III regulations.	No need for space qualified materials in Antarctica demo. Flight demo will conform to JSC 20584, [RD5].	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-8040	TAS-I	The ISPR shall support fire suppression capability.	For instance presence of port(s) for the fire extinguisher.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis
ISPR-8050	TAS-I	The ISPR parts shall be able to sustain application of the fire suppression method.	For instance pressure produced by the fire extinguisher.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis
ISPR-8060	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide means of restoration of the growth chamber environment, at least	This includes removal of combustion products from the growth chamber	System Level: Review of Design

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Safety requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		to reach degraded conditions.	air.	Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis
ISPR-8070	TAS-I	When electrical, biological, optical, sharp edges/points, or other hazards are identified by safety personnel, an appropriate label shall be applied in a prominent location.	Antarctica station applicable standards shall be followed. The future flight demo developer shall use decals conforming to JSC 27260, [RD6].	System Level: Review of Design, Inspection Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis, Inspection

5.3.9 Payload cultivation subsystems main support requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Payload cultivation subsystems main support requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-9010	TAS-I	The 2 Plant Growth Chambers (including root module, illumination module and atmosphere management module) shall have the following enveloping dimensions: Small growth chamber: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 460 mm wide - 720 mm deep - 390 mm high Large growth chamber: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 460 mm wide - 720 mm deep - 830 mm high. 	In analogy with EDR2 Experiment Inserts (EI) available volume. Total production area provided by 2 Plant Growth Chambers to be approximately 0.5 - 1 m ² . CE Study: Dimensions provide 0.66 m ² production area.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test
ISPR-9020	TAS-I	The internal surfaces of the plant cultivation modules shall be highly reflective.	Needed to increase the light absorbed by the plants. Requirement to be implemented to the maximum extent possible.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Payload cultivation subsystems main support requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-9030	TAS-I	<p>The ISPR shall provide a nutrient delivery system (NDS) to the payload cultivation modules that supports the following functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient storage - Water storage (DI or humidity condensate) - Acid or base storage - Replenishment nutrient solution (A,B) storage (see Table 4.103 of BVAD 2015 for composition) - Nutrient solution quality control (EC, pH, temperature, bacteria, particulate, organics) - Nutrient solution and DI water distribution - Root zone/plant support, including physical support, nutrient solution buffer and root aeration. 	<p>From now on, the following nomenclature is assumed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient Storage (NS) - Water Storage (WS) - Acid/Base Storage (AS) Replenishment Solution storage (RS) <p>Current understanding is that “control” will be performed by proper design or on/off-line monitoring and counteraction or external water supply treatment and quality verification (a trade-off is expected). A “mixing” capability is also expected to be implemented to ensure homogenization.</p>	<p>System Level: Review of Design</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design</p>
ISPR-9040	TAS-I	<p>The NDS shall be composed of :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient distribution system - Nutrient storage system <p>The Nutrient storage system shall be divided into:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient Storage (NS) - Water Storage (WS) - Acid/Base Storage (AS) <p>Replenishment solutions Storage (RS-A, RS-B).</p>		<p>System Level: Review of Design, Inspection, Analysis, Test</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis</p>
ISPR-9050	TAS-I	<p>The acid storage, base storage and RS shall provide the amounts necessary for a full life cycle of the most requiring selected crop, considering humidity</p>	<p>There is the need to minimize the manual maintenance requirements also for the Antarctica campaign (i.e. in case of lim-</p>	<p>System Level: Review of Design, Test</p> <p>Equipment</p>

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Payload cultivation subsystems main support requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		<p>ty condensate recovering</p> <p>The NS shall be designed taking into account maximum growth cycle uptake and contingency needs (2.1 times the growth cycle uptake). Long term storage shall not affect the risk of biological, chemical or particulate contamination.</p> <p>Solutions composition and quality shall be compliant with what is defined by the project scientific board.</p>	<p>ited access to container facility in bad weather conditions).</p>	<p>Level: Analysis</p>
ISPR-9060	TAS-I	<p>The nutrient solution storage shall provide fluidic interfaces compatible with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Up to 4 replenishment/adjustment solutions^a, - Up to 2 DI/humidity condensate external supply^{a, b} - nutrient delivery system for root module periodical flushing - drain tank. <p>^aWater shall be supplied to points of use in conformance with the interface specifications for water temperature and quality.</p> <p>^bProcessed waste water shall meet specified quality requirements for further use.</p>	<p>Compatibility tests are assumed to be not necessary as commercial and well-known materials are expected to be selected.</p>	<p>System Level: Review of Design</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design, Inspection</p>

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Payload cultivation subsystems main support requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-9070	TAS-I	The root module shall provide the capability to dispose excess water through continuous recirculation and evaporation.		System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Inspection
ISPR-9080	TAS-I	The acid storage, base storage, and replenishment solutions storage reservoirs shall allow draining activities (e.g. pressurizing port or pump interface).		System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Inspection
ISPR-9090	TAS-I	The solutions storage reservoirs shall be designed as accessible for preventive complete replacement with spare equipment unit (ready to use, not included in the ISPR structure).	The preferred solution is a periodical maintenance instead of a corrective maintenance, which would require quantity levels monitoring system and dedicated interface for each reservoir.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Inspection
ISPR-9100	TAS-I	The nutrient delivery system shall be designed to provide its nominal performance both in continuous and in cyclic operation.		System Level: Analysis Equipment Level: Analysis, Test
ISPR-9110	TAS-I	The nutrient delivery system shall prevent solutions quality variations in case of long-term non-operative conditions for up to 1 month.	To be verified with DLR if preferred to prepare solutions on-site.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test
ISPR-9120	TAS-I	The nutrient delivery system shall meet its performance requirements both in 1g and micro-g conditions.	Design adjustments between ground and flight design are assumed as necessary. Micro-g performance is to	System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level:

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Payload cultivation subsystems main support requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
			be demonstrated on ISS by future flight demo.	Analysis
ISPR-9130	TAS-I	<p>The ISPR shall provide for health and status monitoring of the following parameters of the payload cultivation modules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient solution: quantity level, EC, pH, temperature - Root module: moisture level, EC, pH, temperature - Growth chamber atmosphere: temperature, RH, CO₂ conc, O₂ conc, pressure - Power, C&DH: temperature - Illumination: LED health <p>Monitoring accuracies shall be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient Solution EC: 0.5 to 3.0 mS/cm ± 0.1 mS/cm. - Nutrient Solution pH: 5.0 to 8.0 ± 0.1 - Root Module EC: 0.5 to 3.0 mS/cm ± 0.2 mS/cm. - Root Module pH: 5.0 to 8.0 ± 0.2 	Parameters to be confirmed and accuracies to be provided by Plants quality Responsible.	<p>System Level: Review of Design, Test</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test</p>
ISPR-9140	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide for video monitoring of the payload cultivation chambers.	<p>Applicable only if final configuration will allow meaningful camera position.</p> <p>CE Study: 1x video camera per Plant Growth Chamber to be mounted at top of chamber with vertical view downwards.</p>	<p>System Level: Review of Design, Test</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design</p>
ISPR-9150	TAS-I	The ISPR shall support a monitoring method to identify microorganisms dangerous for crop health and food safety.	Air sampling using Airbus E-nose application could allow "smelling profile" specific of parasites and pathogens.	<p>System Level: Review of Design</p> <p>Equipment Level:</p>

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Payload cultivation subsystems main support requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
				Analysis, Test
ISPR-9160	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide method(s) to monitor total microbiological contamination load in the growth chamber and in the liquid loop.	Since rapid, automated, in line monitoring systems are not in the project scope, at least a sampling port shall be implemented.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design
ISPR-9190	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide methods to prevent microbiological contamination of surfaces in the growth chamber and in the fluid loops.	In particular, via materials selection, surface treatment (e.g.: finishing), and/or exploitation of bactericide.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis
ISPR-9180	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide methods to mitigate microbiological contamination of surfaces and fluids, while avoiding chemical contaminating residues.	The treatment can be very narrow-banded, if specific targets are detected e.g. via E-Nose.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis
ISPR-9190	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide methods to remove ethylene and other trace chemical contaminants.		System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Analysis, Test
ISPR-9200	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide prevention of cross-contamination (trace gas, bacteria, viruses, particulate) between different growth volumes, and between growth volumes and crew compartment.	If the Antarctica test campaign will highlight necessity of maintaining separation from cabin air during manual operations in the growth chamber(s), methods could be contrived for the future flight demo.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis
ISPR-9210	TAS-I	The ISPR shall provide a controlled environment to the shoot zone of the plant growth	All these levels are confirmed by the project scientific advisory board.	System Level: Review of Design, Test

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Payload cultivation subsystems main support requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		chamber, as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • O₂ = 21% to 24% % • CO₂ = 200-1000 ± 50 ppm • Ethylene (produced by plants) less than 50 ppb • TGCS. = 24°C ± 1.5°C • TGCT = 26°C ± 1.5°C • RH = 70% ±15 % • Air flow = 0.3-0.7 ± 0.1 m/s • Light level = 100-600 ± 50 μmol/m²/s • P = 1.0 ±0.1 bar 		Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis
ISPR-9220	TAS-I	The following materials are non-desirable in the plant cultivation chambers and should be avoided for structural components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polyethylene - Metallic coatings such as brass, copper, zinc - Plastics with high level of plasticizers or non-healthy plasticizers such as butyl-phythalates - PVC - Styrofoam bits 	Polyethylene may off-gas ethylene. Brass, copper, zinc may leach into water. PVC and Styrofoam bits (e.g. for shipping) are not recommended by Madrid Antarctic protocol.	Inspection
ISPR-9230	TAS-I	The following materials shall be used as far as possible for surfaces in the plant cultivation chambers that are in contact with water: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stainless steel - Glass - Teflon - Polypropylene - Baked enamels 	Requirement only applies to water for irrigation purposes. LED cooling water is exempt from this requirement.	Inspection
ISPR-9240	TAS-I	The following materials shall be avoided in the plant cultivation chamber materials if ozone is to be used as bacterial sterilizer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Buna-N (Nitrile) - Natural rubber - Nylon - Steel (mild, HSLA) - Zinc 		Inspection

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > ISPR detailed requirements > Payload cultivation subsystems main support requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
ISPR-9250	TAS-I	The Plant Growth Chamber drawers shall be removable from the ISPR.		Inspection

5.4 Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements

The following requirements cover all the structural, power, environmental and resources for the FEG. Since most of the subsystem facilities for the FEG are provided by the Service Section they are not repeated in this chapter. Also not included are the requirements or criteria for the selection of plant types. These are addressed in the EDEN ISS Plant Analysis Report, [RD4].

5.4.1 Structural and mechanical requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Structural and mechanical requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-1010	DLR	The FEG shall be housed in a standard 20-foot high-cube container.		Inspection
FEG-1020	DLR	The FEG shall provide a transparent access door from the service container and an emergency exit door at the other end.	The transparent access door shall be fitted with a curtain to shade FEG when visual access from Service Section not required.	Inspection
FEG-1030	DLR	The FEG emergency exit door shall be dimensioned to allow personnel in emergency climate protection clothing to exit without hindrance.		Inspection, Demonstration
FEG-1040	DLR	The FEG shall have provision for a set of climate protection clothing near the emergency exit door.	As a result of the EDEN ISS setup at NM-III it has been decided that there shall be no climate protection clothing provided in the FEG due to lack of storage volume near the emergency exit door. In worst case personnel can run the 400 m to the station. Although there are obviously some extreme exceptions, personnel will have access to clothes in the cold porch. If there is a really bad emergency that personnel have to get out of the FEG emergency exit door than it is highly likely that they would not have time to grab much in the way of clothing. But considering the station is only 400 m away – this is still a survivable distance even in some of the worst out-	Requirement not to be verified

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Structural and mechanical requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
			side conditions. (plus it could still be possible to run around to the other side of the MTF to grab clothing).	
FEG-1050	DLR, AS	The FEG shall provide a seed germination and initial growth phase facility (nursery).	The FEG nursery shall be a normal shelved section of the FEG but devoted to germination and early growth.	Inspection

5.4.2 Environmental and thermal requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Environmental and thermal requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-3010	AS	The environmental control system shall actively control the following overall FEG ambient atmospheric parameters at canopy level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - temperature 16 – 30 °C - relative humidity 70+/- 5% - air flow plant growth units: 0.4 m/s (target) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature controlled at level required for successful plant growth as well as acceptable for human comfort. - Relative humidity controlled such that dew point does not lead to condensation on internal surfaces and subsequent risk of microbial and fungal growth. - ppO₂ partial pressure controlled to avoid elevated levels from plant growth. - ppCO₂ partial pressure controlled to assure no dangerous concentration for visiting personnel. 	Test
FEG-3020	AS, DLO	The environmental control system shall monitor and control the concentration of the following ambient atmosphere	ppCO ₂ concentration can be increased if necessary by using feeder line from CO ₂ gas bottles stored	Test

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Environmental and thermal requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		parameters in the FEG: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ppCO₂ - ppO₂ - Relative humidity - Temperature - Air flow rate - Pressure differential 	external to the MTF. CDR input: Trace contaminants e.g. C ₂ H ₄ shall be removed by filter but not measured. CDR input: Inlet and outlet ducts of the Air Management System (AMS) in the Service Section AMS rack shall house the following check point sensors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - O₂ (1x in the AMS inlet duct)) - Combined relative humidity and temperature sensors (1x each in the AMS inlet and outlet ducts) - Pressure differential (1x) - Air flow rate (1x) 	
FEG-3030	AS	The environmental control system shall remove and filter FEG ambient atmospheric trace contaminants, particulates, and microbial contamination.	CDR input: Ethylene shall be removed by filter but not measured.	Test
FEG-3040	AS	Temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ , and light sensors shall be deployed inside the FEG in order to have punctual measurements of these parameters.	CDR input: The following sensors shall be deployed inside the FEG to provide punctual measurements for the AMS: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Combined temperature, relative humidity, CO₂ and light sensors (2x) - Combined temperature and relative humidity sensors (4x). 	Inspection Test

5.4.3 Command and data handling requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Command and data handling requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-4010	TPZ	The FEG science telemetry parameters to be monitored by the data handling system shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Science parameters to be monitored by MTF data handling subsystem and distributed to monitors of user community.	Test
FEG-4020	TPZ	The FEG environmental data parameters to be monitored by the data handling system shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Environmental parameters to be monitored by MTF data handling subsystem and distributed to monitors of user community.	Test
FEG-4030	TPZ	The FEG LED Panel data parameters to be monitored by the data handling system shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	LED Panel data parameters to be monitored by MTF data handling subsystem and distributed to monitors of user community.	Test
FEG-4040	TPZ	The FEG nutrient delivery system data parameters to be monitored by the data handling system shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Nutrient delivery system data parameters to be monitored by MTF data handling subsystem and distributed to monitors of user community.	Test
FEG-4050	TPZ	The FEG Environmental Control System commands that are executable from the system monitors in the MTF, Neumayer Station III, the DLR Control Center and applicable remote users shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Need to select environmental parameters and set points. Commands can only be issued remotely after approval by EDEN ISS scientist in Neumayer Station III.	Test
FEG-4060	TPZ	The FEG lighting system commands that are executable from the system monitors in the MTF, Neumayer Station III, the DLR Control Center and applicable remote users shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Need to select LED panel illumination parameters and set points. Commands can only be issued remotely after approval by EDEN ISS scientist in Neumayer Station III.	Test
FEG-4070	TPZ	The FEG nutrient delivery system commands that are executable from the system monitors in the MTF, Neumayer Station III, the DLR Control Center and applicable remote users shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Need to select nutrient delivery system parameters and set points.	Test

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Command and data handling requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		tors in the MTF, Neumayer Station III, the DLR Control Center and applicable remote users shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Commands can only be issued remotely after approval by EDEN ISS scientist in Neumayer Station III.	
FEG-4080	TPZ	The FEG shall provide video monitoring and video teleconferencing facilities.	Video monitoring of plant growth units. Visiting personnel may need video teleconferencing facilities to communicate both with Neumayer Station III and DLR Control Center/User Home Bases.	Inspection

5.4.4 Plant illumination requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Plant illumination requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-5010	HS	The total power consumption for the LED lighting of each plant tray shall not exceed 240 W.	Presently at 125 W per tray at 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ light level at 15 cm above tray.	Test
FEG-5020	HS	The LED panels shall provide lighting with light emission spectra tailored to specific requirements of the plants to be grown.	The LED types shall be chosen based on the plant types defined in [RD4].	Test
FEG-5030	HS	The LED panels shall each have four LED channels that can be individually dimmed. The LEDs shall be made up of sets of 450 nm, 660 nm, 735 nm and 5700K LEDs.	CE Study requirement.	Test
FEG-5040	HS	The LED panels shall provide the following PAR capability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tall plants up to 600 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ - short plants up to 300 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ - nursely 200 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ 	CE Study: Max PAR in nursely: 200 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Measured 15 cm above tray tops.	Test

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Plant illumination requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-5050	HS	Each plant tray will have a single LED panel.	CE Study requirement.	Inspection
FEG-5060	HS	Each LED panel shall have a temperature sensor and over temperature protection.	CE Study requirement.	Test
FEG-5070	HS	Each LED panel shall be water cooled via the MTF Thermal Control System such that the maximum operating temperature of each panel does not exceed 50 °C.	CE Study requirement. LED output efficiency is stable between 20-40 °C. 50 °C to be used as upper limit. Matches past HS product limits.	Test
FEG-5080	HS	Each LED panel shall have a control / power distribution box that accepts an Ethernet connector and 48 VDC power feed.	Feeding each LED panel with 230 VAC (the internal conversion done within the LED is actually irrelevant on the system level and can be left out of this document).	Requirement not to be verified
FEG-5090	HS	Each LED panel shall be monitored for the following parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Status per panel LED (Status) - Set point per panel LED (S_450, S_660, S_735, S_5700) [2 byte integer] - Temperature per bar in the panel LED (T1, T2, T3) [2 byte integer] 1/10 degC - Current per bar LED (I1, I2, I3) [2 byte integer] milliamp - HW configuration LED HW_config [String] - FW version LED FW_version [String] 	CE Study requirement.	Test

5.4.5 Safety requirements

The following are specific safety requirements related to the caution and warning system and fire detection only. The overall FEG safety requirements are included in section 4.2.12.

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Safety requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-6010	AS	Specific AMS control sensor signals shall be used to provide critical environmental data to the overall MTF Caution and Warning system monitoring. Personnel shall be alerted when ambient monitored parameters exceed allowed limits. These safety related AMS sensor signals shall be in addition to the MTF stand-alone safety system.	Caution and warning telemetry displayed on FEG monitor in Service Section and on Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor.	Inspection, Test

5.4.6 Plant grow rack requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Plant growth unit requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-7010	DLR	The FEG plant growing facilities shall comprise two rows of plant grow racks, one row each along the long walls of the container.	Eight racks total within the FEG (see Figure 2-2)	Inspection
FEG-7020	DLR	The plant grow racks shall each be bolted to load bearing points on the container walls and floor and assure there is 8.5 cm free space on the rear side for air ducts and utility lines.	Rear free space needed for accommodating air and water/nutrient lines and telemetry harness. (Space required for manual access)	Inspection
FEG-7030	DLR	The plant grow trays shall have maximum dimensions of (foot-print): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 60 cm length - 40 cm width 	Rack depth shall allow for at least 100 cm walkway down middle of container and enough space for working with plant grow trays.	Inspection
FEG-7040	DLR	Each plant grow rack shall be able to accommodate up to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 plant grow trays with a growth height of 24 cm - 4 plant grow trays with a growth height of 76 cm - 2 plant grow trays with a growth height of 180 cm. 	Choice and number of plant growth tray types depends on possible plant height. The 'plant growth height' excludes LED panels and space for air ducts and water/nutrient lines. Assumed minimum space between LED and top of	Inspection

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Plant growth unit requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
			plant canopy is 15 cm.	
FEG-7050	DLR	Each plant grow tray shall provide the following facilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - light tight enclosure providing at least 5 cm height for plant roots - interchangeable lid with holes to optimize crop spacing - LED panel - water/nutrient feeder lines and return lines 	CE Study: Root zone box height for short crops may be 5 cm. Taller crops may be up to 12 cm in height (or all the same for commonality).	Inspection
FEG-7060	DLR	The plant grow racks shall be constructed using materials that do not corrode in the humidity/temperature environment of the FEG or release chemicals hazardous to human health.		Inspection
FEG-7070	DLR	The plant grow racks shall be constructed such that the plant root compartment is sealed as much as possible to the external environment.	To simulate potential space application, need to avoid liquid leaks outside of root chamber.	Inspection
FEG-7080	DLR	The following materials are non-desirable in the plant cultivation modules and should be avoided for structural components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polyethylene - Metallic coatings such as brass, copper, zinc - Plastics with high level of plasticizers or non-healthy plasticizers such as butyl-phythalates - PVC - Styrofoam bits 	<p>Polyethylene may off-gas ethylene.</p> <p>Brass, copper, zinc may leach into water.</p> <p>PVC and Styrofoam bits (e.g. for shipping) are not recommended by Madrid Antarctic protocol.</p>	Inspection
FEG-7090	DLR	The following materials shall be used as far as possible for surfaces in the plant cultivation modules that are in contact with water: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stainless steel - Glass - Teflon 	Requirement only applies to water for irrigation purposes. LED cooling water is exempt from this requirement.	Inspection

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Plant growth unit requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polypropylene - Baked enamels 		
FEG-7100	UoG	<p>The following materials shall be avoided in the plant cultivation modules materials if ozone is to be used as bacterial sterilizer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Buna-N (Nitrile) - Natural rubber - Nylon - Steel (mild, HSLA) - Zinc 		Inspection
FEG-7110	TPZ	Cameras for monitoring shall be installed to view each plant tray shelf to monitor plant growth.		Inspection

5.4.7 Nutrient delivery system requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Nutrient delivery system requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-8010	UoG	The NDS shall continuously supply pre-defined water/nutrient mix to the plant growth units when activated.	Autonomous control based on pre-defined water/nutrient parameters.	Test
FEG-8020	UoG	The NDS shall provide the capability to house 2 different bulk nutrient solutions and to distribute these solutions to each individual tray within the FEG.		Inspection
FEG-8030	UoG	The NDS shall provide capability to manually resupply micro- and macronutrients, water.	Need to re-supply NDS system depending on use of supplies.	Inspection
FEG-8040	UoG	The NDS shall be activated/deactivated either manually or remotely by telecom-	Need to be activated/deactivated manually for maintenance etc.	Test

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Nutrient delivery system requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		mand.		
FEG-8050	UoG	The NDS shall provide the water and nutrients directly to the plant roots in the plant growth units using an aeroponic and/or hybrid aeroponic/nutrient film technique system.	Aeroponic listed a key technology to test in EDEN ISS proposal.	Test, Inspection
FEG-8060	UoG	The NDS shall provide sensors and sensor logic for monitoring all the parameters defined in section 5.4.3.	Monitored telemetry from FDS sensors used both for NDS control logic and as scientific data.	Inspection, Test
FEG-8070	UoG	The NDS shall support the capability to accept and implement the software commands defined in section 5.4.3.	Need to be able to manually issue commands to NDS to change status of system parameters as required.	Inspection, Test
FEG-8080	DLO, DLR	The NDS shall use the following nutrient chemical components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - NH_4NO_3 - $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{FeN}_3\text{NaO}_{10}$ (Fe-chelate DTPA) - CaCl_2 - KNO_3 - MgSO_4 - $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - K_2SO_4 - KH_2PO_4 - - $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ - $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 	DLO developed recipes.	Inspection
FEG-8090	UoG	The NDS shall autonomously control the nutrient pH using the following chemicals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nitric acid - Potassium hydroxide 	Need to keep pH of nutrient mix at pre-defined level.	Test
FEG-8100	UoG	The NDS shall assure that no pathogens accumulate in the	Need to keep the system free of all pathogens to	Requirement not to be veri-

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Nutrient delivery system requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		system particularly on critical items such as pipe joints, valves and tanks.	avoid plant contamination and compromising food safety as well as plant health. This requirement is not possible to meet at 100% - and thus requirement FEG-8120 is sufficient to see that we are disinfecting to the extent possible, but there may still – as is almost always the case – something living in the hydroponic solution.	fied.
FEG-8110	UoG	The FEG shall provide for the recycling of water/nutrients to the maximum extent possible.	Waste liquid/nutrient recycling system needed to reduce consumables as far as possible. Need to monitor pH of liquid.	N/A, Inspection ('to the extent possible' not verifiable)
FEG-8120	UoG	The NDS shall provide a disinfection system for recycling used liquid back to the plant growth units.	Need to demonstrate future potential space application and minimize water usage. Baselined UV or ozone based system.	Inspection
FEG-8130	UoG	The NDS shall provide for waste liquid disposal by draining to MTF waste tank.	Need to remove waste liquid from system when no longer suitable for use (e.g. high microbial load, too uncertain nutrient ion concentrations).	Inspection, Test
FEG-8140	UoG	The Service Section shall house two 250 L tanks for storage of bulk nutrient solution for the FEG plant trays.	Each reservoir nominally running at a level of 200 L with a 50 L buffer.	Inspection
FEG-8150	UoG	The Cold Porch sub-floor shall house a 250 to 300 L tank for storage of fresh water.		Inspection
FEG-8160	UoG	The Cold Porch sub-floor shall house a 250 to 300 L tank for storage of waste water.	CE Study: Waste tank is in sub-floor of Cold Porch.	Inspection
FEG-8170	UoG	The NDS shall provide for easy sampling and analysis of the bulk as well as waste nutrient solutions.	Need to check status of contaminants in NDS.	Inspection, Test
FEG-8180	UoG	The NDS shall include sensors that permit the offline measurement of the following pa-		Inspection

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Nutrient delivery system requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		rameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pH - EC - Select (2-4) number of nutrient ions - Dissolved oxygen 		
FEG-8190	UoG	The NDS shall recirculate the 'same' primary nutrient solution (with appropriate adjustment) for a minimum period of 4 weeks.	Desire to reduce wastewater from the MTF.	Test
FEG-8200	UoG	The following materials are non-desirable in the NDS and should be avoided for structural components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polyethylene - Metallic coatings such as brass, copper, zinc - Plastics with high level of plasticizers or non-healthy plasticizers such as butyl-phythalates - PVC - Styrofoam bits 	Polyethylene may off-gas ethylene. Brass, copper, zinc may leach into water. PVC and Styrofoam bits (e.g. for shipping) are not recommended by Madrid Antarctic protocol.	Inspection
FEG-8210	UoG	The following materials shall be used as far as possible for surfaces in the NDS that are in contact with water: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stainless steel - Glass - Teflon - Polypropylene - Baked enamels 		Inspection
FEG-8220	UoG	The following materials shall be avoided in the NDS materials if ozone is to be used as bacterial sterilizer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Buna-N (Nitrile) - Natural rubber - Nylon - Steel (mild, HSLA) - Zinc 	Reference CE Study report.	Inspection

5.4.8 Mobile Platform requirements

Note: The following requirements related to the Mobile Platform shall be treated as historical information only because this device is presently on cost grounds not included in the MTF baseline. The requirements shall be treated as a basis for any future decision to include the Mobile Platform in the MTF implementation.

For detailed requirements specific to the mobile platform please reference the separate *EDEN ISS-TPZ-WP3.5-Mobile Platform Specifications-v1.0* document.

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Mobile Platform requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-9010	TPZ	The Mobile Platform shall provide a mount for video camera that can be moved both horizontally the full length of the FEG and vertically the full height of the plant grow racks using a Cartesian robot principle.	Needed for remote visual monitoring of plant growth health and status.	Inspection Test
FEG-9020	TPZ	The Mobile Platform shall have a width < 80 cm.	Need to operate in the 100 cm wide center aisle.	Inspection
FEG-9030	TPZ	The Mobile Platform shall be mounted on a guide rail fixed to the ceiling of the FEG and running the length of the FEG.	Ceiling mounted guide rail needed to keep FEG center aisle free for personnel.	Inspection
FEG-9040	TPZ	The Mobile Platform shall be maneuverable using a handheld controller in the FEG.	Visiting personnel need to have possibility to move Mobile Platform to any position.	Test
FEG-9050	TPZ	The Mobile Platform position shall be remotely controllable by any authorized user.	Needed for remote operator to check specific plant grow tray status.	Test
FEG-9060	TPZ	The Mobile Platform shall have the following video cameras for monitoring plant health: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HD Visual camera - HD video adapted for chlorophyll fluorescence visualization - Infra-red camera 		Inspection
FEG-9070	TPZ, DLR	The Mobile Platform shall not hinder the crew to use the emergency exit hatch at any given time (e.g. operation mode, parking position).		Test
FEG-9080	TPZ	The Mobile Platform data parameters to be monitored by the data handling system shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Mobile Platform data parameters to be monitored by MTF data handling subsystem and distributed to monitors of user community.	Test

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Mobile Platform requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FEG-9090	TPZ	The Mobile Platform commands that are executable from the system monitors in the MTF, Neumayer Station III, the DLR Control Center and applicable remote users shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Need to select Mobile Platform parameters and set points. Commands can only be issued remotely after approval by EDEN ISS scientist in Neumayer Station III.	Test

5.4.9 Food Quality requirements

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Food quality requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
FQ-010	DLR, DLO, CNR, LIT	The following plant quality “quick-test” analyses shall be performed at Neumayer Station III / MTF: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chlorophyll content - Colour - Nitrate concentration - Index of refraction (Brix%) - Firmness/ripeness (penetrometer) - Horticultural measurements 	Responsibility of EDEN ISS personnel in Antarctica. Need to develop procedures and test prior to MTF operations. EDEN ISS responsible personnel need to be trained.	Test of procedures.
FQ-20	DLR, DLO, CNR, LIT	The FEG plants and growth parameters including illumination and nutrient mix shall be replicated in home laboratories.	Need to compare EDEN ISS FEG environment with home laboratory environment.	Inspection
FQ-30	LIT, CNR	Analytical procedures shall be developed for determining the following food quality parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Carbohydrates - Organic acids - Nutraceuticals (fibre, vitamins, polyphenols, 	Post-EDEN ISS analyses to be performed on samples returned from Antarctica.	Test of procedures

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Food quality requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
		flavonoids, anthocyanins, glucosinolates, carotenoids, chlorophylls) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minerals - Fats - Anti-nutritionals (NO₃, oxalic acid) - Others 		
FQ-40	CNR, ADS, DLR, DLO	Certain harvested food shall be checked for the following common pathogens: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total microbial count - Lactic acid bacteria - Molds and yeasts - Total coliforms - Escherichia coli - Salmonella - Staphylococci 	Both pre- and post-harvest.	Test of procedures
FQ-50	DLR, LIT, CNR	Some samples of food harvested for human consumption shall be kept in 'sample bags' that will be stored in varied conditions (freeze dried or frozen to -40 degC) for their long term storage until returned for sample analysis in home laboratories		Requirement not to be verified. Test of harvesting procedures.

5.4.10 Plant health monitoring and horticulture requirements

Note: The plant selection shall be defined in the EDEN ISS Plant Analysis Report, [RD4].

Mobile Test Facility detailed requirements > Future Exploration Greenhouse detailed requirements > Plant health monitoring and horticultural requirements				
ID	Applicability	Requirement	Rationale / Comments	Verification Method
PHM-010	DLO	The FEG plant cultivation shall produce > 150 kg of fresh weight per year.	CE Study: Daily rate shall vary between 0 to 750 g depending on FEG operational status.	N/A. Requirement to be considered as guideline.

6 System test requirements

The EDEN ISS system test requirements shall be defined in a separate document (EDEN ISS-DLR-WP4.4-AIT Plan-v0.3)

The system test shall be performed at the DLR and continued at the Neumayer Station III with the fully integrated MTF and the communications with the ECC and remote users.

7 Requirements verification

The verification of the requirements in section 5 shall be controlled via a separate Verification Control Document (VCD), see Annex A. The VCD shall use the template example in Table 7-1.

The table columns shall contain the following information for tracking the requirement close-out:

Column 1: Requirement ID as in section 5 of this document

Column 2: Requirement short description

Column 3: Verification method. The methods to be used are:

Inspection (I): Inspection is defined in this document as either a visual check, or a simple measurement (requiring no specialized equipment) to verify a component or sub-system parameter (e.g. mass or length) without requiring the component or sub-system to be active.

Analysis (A): Analysis is defined in this document as the verification via calculation or (computer-based) simulation of component, sub-system or system performance using industry-standard methods and margins.

Test (T): Testing is defined in this document as a measurement of component, sub-system or system parameter(s) and/or capabilities that require the use of specialized equipment or require the component, sub-system or system to be active.

Demonstration (D): Demonstration is defined in this document as any verification of crew procedures or protocols, as well as the verification of the interface / interaction between human and component, subsystem or system.

Review of Design (R): Review of Design is defined in this document as verification of a requirement by reviewing the applicable design documentation.

N/A: A requirement is either not verifiable or is verifiable but it is opted not to verify on account of excessive costs, time delays or other reasons.

Column 4: Verification close-out status and comments

8 References

8.1 *Applicable Documents*

[AD1] Antarctic Treaty. "The protocol on environmental protection of the Antarctic Treaty," Madrid, Spain, 1991.

8.2 *Reference Documents*

[RD1] ESA, "Technology Readiness Levels Handbook for Space Applications", ESA, Noordwijk, The Netherlands, 2008.

[RD2] International Standard Payload Rack to NASA/ESA/JAXA Modules Interface Control Document, SSP 41002, Revision P, 28 March, 2011.

[RD3] Columbus Pressurized Payloads Interface Requirements Document, COL-RIBRE-SPE-0164, Issue 2, dated 01.11.2010.

[RD4] EDEN ISS Plant Analysis Report.

[RD5] Spacecraft Maximum Allowable Concentrations for Airborne Contaminants, JSC 20584, NASA JSC, November, 2008.

[RD6] Decal Process Document and Catalog, JSC 27260F, NASA JSC, January 2010.

9 Annex A: System Requirements Verification Control Document

System Requirements Verification Control Document

prepared for

WP 2.1 - System Requirements & Interface Analysis

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Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
0.1	2018-01-26	See list of authors	Initial Release
0.2	2018-03-23	See list of authors	<p>Removed verification matrix column "Verification Closeout Reference" and changed column "Comments" to "Verification Close-out".</p> <p>Changed verification method to "Not to be verified" for the following requirements: FEG-5080 FEG-8100 FQ-60 ME-330 ISPR-9240</p> <p>Explanation provided in the "Verification Close-out" column.</p> <p>Modified requirement AL-80 from 2x 230 V power outlets to 1x 230 V power outlet</p>
1.0	2018-04-09	See list of authors	Final Release

Executive summary

This document provides the System Requirements Verification Control Document (VCD) of the EDEN ISS project. The VCD provides for tracking the close-out of the system requirements verification.

Requirements verification

The verification of the requirements in the EDEN ISS System Requirements Document shall be controlled by this Verification Control Document (VCD).

The columns contain the following information for tracking the requirement close-out:

Column 1: Requirement ID as in section 5 of System Requirements Document

Column 2: Requirement short description

Column 3: Verification method. The methods used are:

Inspection (I): Inspection is defined in this document as either a visual check, or a simple measurement (requiring no specialized equipment) to verify a component or sub-system parameter (e.g. mass or length) without requiring the component or sub-system to be active.

Analysis (A): Analysis is defined in this document as the verification via calculation or (computer-based) simulation of component, sub-system or system performance using industry-standard methods and margins.

Test (T): Testing is defined in this document as a measurement of component, sub-system or system parameter(s) and/or capabilities that require the use of specialized equipment or require the component, sub-system or system to be active.

Demonstration (D): Demonstration is defined in this document as any verification of crew procedures or protocols, as well as the verification of the interface / interaction between human and component, subsystem or system.

Review of Design (R): Review of Design is defined in this document as verification of a requirement by reviewing the applicable design documentation.

N/A: A requirement is either not verifiable or is verifiable but it is opted not to verify on account of excessive costs, time delays or other reasons.

Column 4: Verification close-out description

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
NM-10	NM-III shall provide electrical power to MTF	Inspection	Verified.
NM-20	NM-III shall provide hardwired fibre optic cable link and wireless LAN	Inspection	Verified. Cable protection added over sections of the cable running along the elevated platform.
NM-30	NM-III shall provide > 5 m ² for EDEN ISS console stations	Inspection	Verified. Post departure of NM-III summer guests provides ample space within the NM-III multipurpose laboratory for the EDEN ISS operations consoles as well as EDEN ISS laboratory equipment.
NM-40	NM-III shall provide 2-way satellite communications link via AWI to DLR, Bremen	Inspection	Verified.
NM-50	NM-III satellite communication link shall provide a bandwidth of > 100 kbps for supporting EDEN ISS data telemetry and commanding and > 250 kbps 4 hours per day video.	Inspection, Test	Verified (partially). The > 100 kbps for supporting EDEN ISS data telemetry and commanding is amply available and video links have been successfully conducted (but not yet for a duration of 4 hours or more per day).
NM-60	NM-III shall provide wetlab facilities for EDEN personnel.	Inspection	Verified.
NM-70	NM-III shall provide internal safe storage container for 150 kg of chemicals.	Inspection	Verified. Some chemicals stored directly within the NM-III multi-purpose lab, others stored in the NM-III dangerous goods storage room (U1 level of the station).
NM-80	NM-III shall provide back-up scientist trained to monitor and operate EDEN ISS.	Inspection	Verified.
NM-90	NM-III shall provide two 20 ft external storage containers.	Inspection	Verified. One external storage container has been provided by AWI and a significant amount of space internal to the Neumayer Station III (on the

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
			gallery) has also been provided. Sufficient for all EDEN ISS storage requirements.
NM-100	NM-III shall provide Skidoos for EDEN ISS personnel as required.	Inspection	Verified.
NM-110	NM-III shall provide up to 400 L/week potable water for EDEN ISS.	Inspection	Verified. MTF log book being used to monitor water use. Greater than 400 L/week was employed during the initial week when the MTF nutrient delivery system was first initiated but the average weekly draw from the facility is considerably less than 400 L.
NM-120	Neumayer Station III shall provide facilities for storage/disposal of all waste from MTF.	Inspection	Verified.
NM-130	20 kg/month of MTF solid waste shall be processed by the existing Neumayer Station III waste handling/protocols.	Demonstrate adherence to protocols during test campaign in Bremen	Verified (this is an average amount spread over the full year).
NM-140	2.5 kg/week of MTF waste biomass shall be processed by the existing Neumayer Station III waste handling/protocols.	Inspection	Verified (this is a worst case average amount spread over the full year).
NM-150	Neumayer Station III nominal waste stream shall support the processing and safe disposal of up to 340 L/week (worst case) of waste nutrient solutions from the EDEN ISS associated activities.	Demonstrate adherence to protocols during test campaign in Bremen	Verified. Actual values have been shown to be considerably less than this via test.
NM-160	Polarstern and Neumayer Station III	Inspection	Verified. Cranes used to offload the containers and subsequently install

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	crane lifting capability for EDEN ISS.		them on the EDEN ISS platform. In the end the EDEN ISS containers were transferred from Cape Town to Antarctica by the South African Agulhas research vessel with a very capable crane.
NM-170	Neumayer Station III shall provide an Elevated Platform for mounting the MTF containers.	Inspection	Verified.
NM-180	Neumayer Station III shall provide an outfitted utility sledge for transport of MTF supplies.	Inspection	Verified. Utility sledge available and modified to suit EDEN ISS water and material transport requirements.
NM-190	An acoustic alarm in Neumayer Station III for smoke/fire and CO ₂ and O ₂ levels exceed pre-defined limits.	Inspection, Test	Verified.
NM-200	The MTF smoke detection system connected to the overall Neumayer Station III fire alarm system by a dedicated cable.	Inspection, Test	Verified.
NM-210	A fixed guiding line shall be established between the MTF and the Neumayer Station III.	Inspection	Verified. Safety line continues further from the MTF to the Neumayer Station III SPUSO.
DLR-10	EDEN ISS Control Center (ECC) at DLR, Bremen, Germany.	Inspection	Verified.
DLR-20	ECC hardware and software applications.	Inspection	Verified.
DLR-30	Back-up ECC.	Inspection	Verified.
DLR-40	ECC 2-way secure Internet and communications bandwidth be-	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	tween AWI and EDEN ISS.	Test bandwidth	
DLR-50	The ECC 2-way secure Internet based communications bandwidth between remote user and EDEN ISS.	Inspection Test bandwidth	Verified.
EUS-10	EDEN ISS User Home Base experiment command and monitoring console station.	Inspection	Verified.
EUS-20	EDEN ISS User Home Base dedicated secure 2-way communications and data transfer link.	Inspection	Verified.
EUS-30	EDEN ISS User Home Base 2-way link with DLR control center data transfer rate 1 Mbps.	Inspection Test data rate	Verified.
EUS-40	EDEN ISS User Home Base shall have the capability to execute a limited set of experiment commands via the ECC.	Demonstration during test campaign in Bremen	Verified.
EUS-50	The EDEN User Home Base facilities support the EDEN ISS Outreach Program	N/A, Demonstration	Verified.
EP-10	The Elevated Platform (EP) structural characteristics.	Inspection	Verified.
EP-20	The EP constructed to be disassembled for storage and transport.	Inspection	Verified.
EP-30	The EP platform attachment points	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	for crane hoisting operations.		
EP-40	The individual parts of the EP platform shall not exceed 10000 kg in mass.	Inspection	Verified.
EP-50	The EP shall be able to support up to 48000 kg loading.	Inspection of “KSF Statische Berechnung” analysis.	Verified.
EP-60	The EP structure temperature tolerance.	Inspection of design documentation	Verified.
EP-70	The EP surface paint coating.	Inspection of design documentation	Verified. That said, the new leg extensions for the EP were brown in colour and different from the nominal white/silver EP colour. Paint properties and corrosion resistance are the same with the brown surface paint.
ME-10	The MTF shall be housed in two (2) 20 ft high-cube containers mounted end-to-end.	Inspection	Verified.
ME-20	The high-cube containers Container Safety Convention (CSC) certification requirements.	Inspection (Tested by container manufacturer)	Verified.
ME-30	The total mass of each container 10000 kg.	Inspection	Verified. All containers less than 10000 kg in their shipping configuration. Reference: 2017-10-04 Tracking of MTF Container Masses – AIT.xlsx. Verified. The shipping masses of the containers were measured as Service section 9.6 ton, FEG container 8.5 ton (metric).
ME-40	The total mass of the final integrated MTF < 48000 kg.	Inspection	Verified via total mass calculation.
ME-50	The raised floor elevated 30 cm from the standard container floor.	Inspection	Verified. 31-32 cm is available.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
ME-60	The sub-floor area free space height of > 25 cm.	Inspection	Verified. Approx. 27 cm is available.
ME-70	The under-floor space sealed for liquid spills/leaks contained within the MTF.	Test	Verified. Tested during AIT phase via many leaks (all sections).
ME-80	The built-in floor loading capability of 300-500 kg/m ² .	Test	Verified. Demonstrated via the installation of several EDEN ISS subsystems.
ME-90	The containers shall be mounted at a height of ca. 2.5 m above ground on the Elevated Platform.	Inspection	Verified.
ME-100	The combined MTF and elevated platform tolerate a maximum continuous wind speed of 50 m/s from any geographical direction.	Inspection of "KSF Statische Berechnung" analysis.	Verified.
ME-110	The MTF shall be set-up approximately 400 m south of the Neumayer Station III.	Inspection, N/A	Verified.
ME-120	The Cold Porch access door faces the minimum seasonal wind speed direction (approximately west).	Inspection, N/A	Verified.
ME-130	The MTF structure to tolerate an external ambient temperature range of -55 to +40°C without incurring structural damage.	Inspection of design documentation	Verified. Certain more temperature sensitive EDEN ISS components were shipped via air freight or Polarstern. Additionally, temperature data loggers were installed in the EDEN ISS containers during shipment and recorded temperature over the logistics chain (including a separate temperature sensor within the seed transport box).
ME-140	The MTF Cold Porch and emergency exit doors operate without defor-	Inspection of design documentation	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	mation problems for an external temperature range and wind speed.		
ME-150	The MTF Cold Porch and emergency exit doors shall both be fully sealed against wind and snow access when closed.	Inspection of design documentation Proven design.	Verified. Periods of high winds and snow during deployment phase doors remained fully sealed.
ME-160	The MTF containers insulated such that the overall thermal transmittance U-value is less than 0.3 – 0.35 W/m ² K.	Analysis	Verified. This was the value utilized in the container design. The first year of overwintering operations will be used to illustrate if this was sufficient for all use cases.
ME-170	The internal wall and ceiling insulation cladding resistance to fixtures of 4000 N pull-out strength.	Analysis, Test	Verified. The internal wall and ceiling insulation cladding fixture installs have been shown to support the installation of all the hardware desired for fixation in this manner.
ME-180	The internal surfaces of the insulation cladding shall be made of washable material.	Inspection, Demonstration	Verified.
ME-190	The external MTF surfaces shall be white (RAL 9010).	Inspection	Verified.
ME-200	The MTF weather sealed access ports for power cable from the Neumayer Station III, and power, data from the interior to the exterior of the MTF.	Inspection	Verified.
ME-210	A vertical ladder attached to the outside of the MTF.	Inspection	Verified.
ME-220	A small safety rail along the longitudinal access of the MTF	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
ME-230	Illumination shall be provided at the exterior of the MTF.	Inspection	Verified.
ME-240	The MTF shall weather sealed access port for thermal lines running to the MTF exterior and CO ₂ lines running in to the MTF.	Inspection	Verified. South side external interface port provides interface for thermal lines (input, output), CO ₂ input line, free cooler power line, CO ₂ heater line.
ME-250	The joints between the insulation plates within the MTF prevent water leaking into the insulation material.	Inspection	Verified.
ME-260	A minimum of 30 cm shall be provided between the containers.	Inspection	Verified.
ME-270	A WLAN antenna on roof of the west-container for data communication to Neumayer Station III.	Inspection	Verified (this is presently the backup communications system, with the primary system being a fibre optic cable running to the Neumayer Station III).
ME-280	The MTF designed such that all electric related harness shall be channeled via the ceiling and fluid lines via the sub-floor.	Inspection	Verified. Cables were only passed in the subfloor area during exceptional cases. In these instances the cables were kept along the top of the subfloor area and not allowed to fall directly onto the floor.
ME-290	The TransMADDS disinfection agent shall not damage specific equipment.	Inspection of manufacturer data sheets and/or Test	Verified. Documentation and/or analysis was conducted for several of the possibly more sensitive pieces of hardware. Operational protocols for some equipment were also built-in to TransMADDS operations (covering of selected hardware such as sensors and cameras). All testing conducted this far with 12% hydrogen peroxide has demonstrated to have no negative influence on installed EDEN ISS hardware.
ME-300	Items to be protected on to avoid residual coatings on MTF sensitive hardware from TransMADDS disin-	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	fection agent,		
ME-310	The E-Nose shall be trained to detect specified pathogens.	Subsystem: Test	Verified during AIT phase and other subsystem level testing.
ME-320	Air intake inlet for the interior Service Section Air Management System mounted on the south side of the west container.	Inspection	Verified.
ME-330	Air outlet for the interior Service Section Air Management System mounted on the south side of the Service Section container.	Not to be verified. See comment.	This requirement is not applicable. No formal separate outlet for the Service Section Air Management System was deemed to be required and the air brought into the Service Section will leak out of the facility via inherent leaks within the Service Section (door, Roxtec interface panels etc.). This is sufficient as the Service Section Air Management System is not used on a regular frequency.
ME-340	Heat rejection unit positioned outside of the MTF to remove excess heat.	Inspection	Verified. The MTF includes a roof mounted freecooler.
ME-350	The MTF interface to mount CO ₂ bottles, and regulation equipment, on the exterior of the container.	Inspection	Verified. Nominally 3 CO ₂ bottles will be mounted along the south wall at any one time, with two bottles active (i.e. connected to the CO ₂ distribution system).
EC-10	The MTF thermally insulated such that internal temperature maintained above 5 °C for at least 45 minutes. Upon power loss or internal system failure.	Analysis, Test	Modeled by EnginSoft (reference: EDEN ISS-ES-WP2.4-D2.6-CFD Simulations Report-v2.1.docx). Results suggest that change from 22 degC to 5 degC occurs in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 49 min when there is a wind speed of 30 m/s and an external temperature of -50 degC • 79 min when there is a wind speed of 30 m/s and an external temperature of -30 degC
EC-20	The MTF electric wall-mounted emergency heaters to maintain	Inspection, Test	Verified. Three wall mounted heaters are included in the system with one heater in the FEG, one in the SS and one in the cold porch. Additional, two

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	internal temperature > 5 °C.		small plug-in heaters are also available for use.
EL-10	The MTF shall worst case operational scenario 55 kW of electrical power.	Analysis, Test	Verified. The 55 kW value is based upon the fact that the NM-III station includes 80 A fuses on the MTF supply line.
EL-20	The MTF electrical power distribution network compatible with the 230V AC, three-phase, 50 Hz supply of the Neumayer Station III.	Inspection, Test	Verified.
EL-30	The MTF uninterruptible power supply provides up to 1400 W for up to 0.5 hours at 70% load for specific MTF systems.	Inspection	Verified. With the actual measured power demand of the UPS being 560 W, the estimated actual runtime of the UPS is 190-200 minutes.
CDH-10	The MTF hard-wired fiber optic cable and a backup wireless LAN connection to support 2-way data transfer with Neumayer Station III with a bandwidth of >1 Mbps.	Inspection of link availability Test of bandwidth	Verified.
AN-10	The acoustic emissions generated by each MTF audible noise source limits.	Test	Verified via test during the AIT phase. Reference 2017-06-08 Messung Bremen Gewächshaus.xlsx for measured noise values.
SW-10	Software applications available to the MTF system monitor, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor, and the ECC.	Inspection	Verified.
SW-20	ISPR software applications available to the MTF system monitor, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS mon-	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	itor, the ECC and applicable EDEN ISS User Home Bases.		
SW-30	Plant grow experiment software applications available to the MTF system monitor, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor, the ECC and applicable EDEN ISS User Home Bases.	Inspection	Verified.
GL-10	The MTF shall provide overhead white light illumination in each enclosed section.	Inspection, Demonstration	Verified.
GL-20	Each of the overhead lights shall be manually controlled by 2-way manual switch.	Demonstration	Verified. On/Off control via Argus software, or manual on/off in Argus box or via power box switches directly.
WM-10	MTF solid waste stored in sealed containers/bags.	Inspection	Verified.
WM-20	MTF liquid waste stored in sealed tanks.	Inspection	Verified. 20 L sealed water canisters used for fresh water and waste water transport to and from the MTF.
WM-30	FEG plant waste stored in sealed containers/bags.	Inspection	Verified.
WM-40	Log record maintained of the amount of waste-water and solid waste produced by the MTF.	Inspection	Verified. Hardcover journal located in the MTF.
WM-50	MTF waste-water and solid waste disposal integrated into NM-III waste management plan.	Inspection	Verified. Waste plan detailed in project UBA application and detailed discussions were had with AWI agree to the specific handling practices of EDEN ISS wastes. All MTF waste water is transported to the NM-III and added to the nominal NM-III waste water stream for processing (including

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
			any project waste water generated in the multipurpose lab). Project bio-waste added to station bio-waste bins. Other traditional plastic, paper, metal etc. waste sorted and added to nominal NM-III waste streams.
ES-10	External stowage container approximately 7-8 km from the Neumayer Station III.	Inspection	During the deployment phase the external storage container was positioned directly in the vicinity of the MTF. Later it was moved to the summer storage location (1-2 km from the NM-III station). At the end of the field season the storage container will be positioned in the winter storage location (7-8 km from NM-III). A wide variety of project items will be stored over winter in the gallery within the NM-III station itself.
ES-20	Items stored in the external stowage container to withstand -50°C to +10.	Analysis, Test	Verified. All items stored in the external storage container over winter were 'certified' by the respective EDEN ISS partner to be storable to -50°C. That said, only a few boxes were stored in the external storage container over winter as a great deal of space was provided directly in the NM-III station itself from project supplies.
T-10	The MTF interiors cleaned and sanitized prior to shipment.	N/A, Inspection	Verified. A comprehensive cleaning procedure was implemented in the SS and FEG prior to shipment. The TransMADDS was also employed (12% hydrogen peroxide).
T-20	Loose items stored safely in containers and/or drawers prior to shipment.	Inspection	Verified. A detailed inspection of the containers was had prior to shipment to ensure all items were appropriately secured.
T-30	ISPR and support equipment in sealed containers when transported from manufacturer to MTF integrator.	Inspection	Verified.
T-40	ISPR and support equipment housed in the MTF Service Section Container for transport by ship to Antarctic.	Inspection	Verified. The ISPR and the bulk of the support equipment was shipped in either the SS, FEG or additional project shipping container for shipment to Antarctica. Two additional ISPR boxes were shipped separate to the three containers out of storage temperature requirements (e.g. the NDS drawer was shipped on the plane to ensure temperature did not drop below freez-

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
			ing).
T-50	During ship transport the MTF designed to be water tight and tolerate temperature and RH ambient parameters.	Inspection	Verified.
MS-10	A Maintenance and Spares policy established by the EDEN ISS project.	Inspection	Verified. A detailed analysis of project spares was conducted. This followed the conduct of a project failures, modes, effects and criticality analysis and resulted in a wide variety of spares being acquired for the project.
MS-20	The Maintenance and Spares policy applicable to all EDEN ISS hardware.	N/A, Inspection	Verified.
MS-30	Hardware developers provide list of life-limited items and define number of spares required for critical items.	Inspection	Verified. Conducted as part of the maintenance and spares analysis.
MS-40	Sufficient chemicals to support complete restart of plant growth experiments in the FEG.	Inspection	Verified.
MS-50	Sufficient chemicals to support 1.5 years of continuous plant grow experiments.	Inspection	Verified. Ca. 2 years of chemicals were shipped with the facility.
MS-60	MTF interior surfaces cleaned at least every 2 months, floors weekly and table tops daily using either isopropyl alcohol or 10% bleach.	Demonstration	Verified. Added to regular procedures list.
S-10	A Safety Training Manual shall be provided by the EDEN ISS project.	Inspection	Verified. Safety training of on-site EDEN ISS personal conducted early in the deployment activities.
S-20	Visiting MTF personnel provide	Inspection	Verified. In addition to the documentation, overwinterers receive orga-

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	written confirmation that they have read and understood the EDEN ISS Safety Training Manual prior to first visit.		nized training related to MTF safety.
S-30	Visiting MTF personnel record name, time of entry and departure in a log-book in the MTF.	Inspection	Verified.
S-40	Safety rails enclosing the following elements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Platform - Access stairs to platform (both sides). 	Inspection	Verified. The platform and stairs to access the platform included safety rails all around. Additionally, a bar is included on the roof of the MTF that EDEN ISS personnel can connect a safety harness to when working on the roof and the ladder accessing the MTF roof includes a safety cage.
S-50	The environmental control system Fire Detection System through-out the MTF that is integrated with the overall MTF caution and warning system.	Inspection	Verified.
S-60	Smoke detectors and O ₂ /CO ₂ safety detectors mounted within each enclosed space of the MTF.	Inspection	Verified. Smoke detectors found in each section (cold porch, service section and FEG), while O ₂ and CO ₂ sensors included in the service section and FEG.
S-70	Smoke detectors and CO ₂ /O ₂ safety detectors backup battery power in case of main power failure.	Inspection, Demonstration	Verified. Several standalone (i.e. battery powered) exist in the facility and the CO ₂ /O ₂ safety system is connected to the power system via the UPS.
S-80	Smoke detectors and O ₂ /CO ₂ safety detectors monitored such that an acoustic alarm is sounded on all EDEN ISS system consoles.	Demonstration	Verified. But the separate HTK O ₂ and CO ₂ safety system includes its own acoustic and visual alarms. The Argus connected smoke detectors results in an Argus acoustic alarm that occurs both in the MTF and in the NM-III station. Stan-alone smoke detectors in the MTF also provide acoustic alarms.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
S-90	Internal emergency exit route clearly marked on MTF floor and over all relevant doors.	Inspection	Verified.
S-100	External emergency exit route indicated both on MTF and Platform.	Inspection	Verified.
S-110	Fire extinguishers provided in each of the sections of the MTF:	Inspection	Verified. CO2 (2 kg) fire extinguishers available in the cold porch and FEG. Power fire extinguisher (6 kg) available in the Service Section.
S-120	All chemical handling by personnel performed with gloves, lab coat and eye protection.	N/A, Inspection	Verified.
S-130	All chemicals brought to or removed from the MTF transported in sealed containers.	N/A, Inspection	Verified.
S-140	Chemical spill during transport between MTF and Neumayer Station III, standard station procedures for clean-up operations.	N/A, Demonstration	Verified.
S-150	A chemical spill kit available to the EDEN ISS personnel in the MTF.	Inspection	Verified. A large (ca. 30 L bucket) is maintained in the MTF for external spills into the snow. Internal spills in the MTF will be cleaned up via the use of either absorbent pillows or paper towels with appropriate personal protective gear worn by the operator.
S-160	Minor chemical spills immediately cleaned by visiting personnel.	N/A, Demonstration	Verified.
S-170	Major chemical spills immediately reported to Neumayer Station III.	N/A, Demonstration	Verified. Handled and reported like any other NM-III spills.
S-180	Visiting personnel wear protective glasses when entering and working	N/A, Demonstration	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	in the MTF FEG.		
S-190	Electrical power points and plugs in the MTF as a minimum meet the European CE standard.	Inspection	Verified.
S-200	Personnel assure there is drinking water available in the MTF at all times.	Inspection, Demonstration	No longer a requirement. The MTF is situated in close enough proximity to NM-III station that this is not a mandatory requirement.
S-210	An emergency first-aid kit provided in the MTF.	Inspection	Verified.
S-220	First-aid kit clearly marked and placed in an easily accessible position (or multiple positions) in the MTF.	Inspection, Demonstration	Verified. First aid kit located directly at entry door into the MTF (cold porch).
S-230	For MTF power and/or lighting system failure, a hand lamp/torch available on an easily accessible and visible wall mounting both in Service Section and the FEG.	Inspection	Verified.
S-240	Climate protection clothing in the FEG in case of emergency exit from MTF.	Inspection	No longer a requirement due to the close proximity of the station (e.g. for emergency escape during a large fire) and that clothes are available by the cold porch entry door (e.g. for use during less critical emergencies).
S-250	Dedicated eye wash station included in the Service Section.	Inspection	Verified. Eye wash station located directly at entry door into the MTF (cold porch).
S-260	Smoke, CO ₂ and O ₂ safety detectors implement an acoustic and visual caution and warning system for	Inspection, Demonstration	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	alerting personnel.		
S-270	Emergency portable lights available in each section of the MTF.	Inspection	Besides flashlights, standalone portable lights are only available in the cold porch. That said, both the Service Section and FEG contain sections of their nominal LED overhead lighting which are battery powered and provided added safety for power failures.
S-280	Fire extinguishers provided in the FEG, Service Section and Cold Porch.	Inspection	Verified.
ANT-10	EDEN ISS project only use sanitized seeds as basis for plant growth investigations.	N/A, Inspection	To the extent possible.
ANT-20	All hardware used in the MTF sterilized prior to use.	Inspection	Verified. Detailed cleaning protocol conducted prior to shipment to Antarctica.
ANT-30	Waste liquids from the FEG stored in dedicated sealed tank in the MTF Service Section container.	Inspection	Verified.
ANT-40	Plant waste shall be stored in sealed containers and removed to the Neumayer Station III for controlled disposal.	Inspection	Verified.
ANT-50	Only food crops will be grown within the MTF.	Inspection	Verified. Only food crops selected and only food crops transported to Antarctica.
ANT-60	MTF shall not use soil.	Inspection	Verified. Aeroponics implemented as primary hydroponic solution delivery method, with some rockwool cubes or cloth grow-mats used to hold seeds in initial position.
ANT-70	No pesticides used as part of the EDEN ISS project.	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
ANT-80	Polystyrene beads, chips or similar forms of packaging not employed for the shipment of EDEN ISS project hardware to Neumayer Station III.	Inspection	Verified. Only large foam or paper packaging pieces used for equipment transport to Antarctica.
ANT-90	Use of PVC is strongly discouraged.	N/A Requirement to be treated as guideline.	Some PVC piping employed in NDS and thermal system piping but all PVC sent to Antarctica will be returned to Europe at project completion.
ANT-100	All persons accessing the hydroponics facility should have clean hands, footwear and clothing.	N/A Requirement to be implemented in Safety Training Manual.	To be implemented.
ANT-110	No food taken into the FEG section of the MTF.	N/A Requirement to be implemented in Safety Training Manual.	To be implemented.
ANT-120	Smokers shall not enter the Service Section or FEG unless they have washed their hands and replaced their clothing.	N/A Requirement to be implemented in Safety Training Manual.	To be implemented.
ANT-130	Invertebrate traps (sticky traps) installed in the MTF and monitored regularly.	Inspection	Verified. Included in operations procedures.
ANT-140	Sealed transport cases used for	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	transport of harvested plant material from the MTF to the NM-III station.		
ANT-150	Non-fruit bearing plants such as herbs not allowed to flower and go to seed.	Inspection	Verified. Included in operations procedures.
ANT-160	In case of inadvertent flowering of non-fruit bearing plants, the flowers removed and incinerated, autoclaved and/or sealed appropriately for removal from Antarctica.	Inspection	Verified. Included in operations procedures.
ANT-170	Plant seeds transported to the Antarctic for the EDEN IS project logged.	Inspection	Verified. Seed log included in seed transport case.
ANT-180	Plants produced in the MTF that are destined for human consumption must be consumed within the NM-III environs.	Inspection	Verified. Included in operations procedures.
AL-10	Cold Porch access door for visiting personnel can be manually operated from both sides.	Inspection, Demonstration	Verified.
AL-20	Cold Porch door window dimensions 40*40 cm.	Inspection	Verified. Final window size 60 cm x 40 cm (height x width)
AL-30	Cold Porch internal manually operated door connects to the Service Section.	Inspection, Demonstration	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
AL-40	Cold Porch minimum floor area of 3.225 m ² .	Inspection	Verified. Overall cold porch area greater than specified value. Remaining useable floor space (without cabinet) is ca. 1.45 m x 1.50 m.
AL-50	Cold Porch provides storage for both external and internal clothing of 3 visiting personnel.	Inspection	Verified.
AL-60	Cold Porch heaters automatically activated by the environmental control system when ambient temperature falls below 5 °C.	Test	Verified. Additionally, heaters are included in the cold porch subfloor which ensure that the water reservoirs do not freeze.
AL-70	Cold Porch provides for video monitoring of visiting personnel activities.	Inspection	No video monitoring planned directly into the cold porch but an external camera (located on the roof of NM-III) provides a view showing personnel visiting the MTF.
AL-80	Cold Porch provides at least one standard 230 V power outlets.	Inspection	Verified.
AL-90	Cold Porch houses the fresh air system (Service Section air management system) of the MTF.	Inspection	Verified.
SS-1010	The Service Section minimum floor area 9.05 m ² .	Inspection	Verified.
SS-1020	The Service Section contains various equipment.	Inspection	Verified.
SS-1030	The Service Section has a window facing the Neumayer Station III.	Inspection	Verified.
SS-1040	The Service Section contains a tool-kit.	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
SS-1050	The Service Section contains a warm water sink.	Inspection, Demonstration	Verified.
SS-1060	The Service Section provides storage facilities for consumables.	Inspection	Verified.
SS-1070	The Service Section provides for the disposal of both liquid and solid waste.	Inspection	Verified. Waste buckets under the sink. Sink drain runs to waste water tank within cold porch.
ET-10	Environmental control system in the Service Section supports specific internal temperature and RH ambient parameter ranges.	ROD	Verified. Temperature and RH control demonstrated in tight tolerances during Antarctic deployment.
ET-20	Environmental control system is designed to exchange air with the external environment.	ROD	Verified. The fresh air system installed in the cold porch provides this service, otherwise exchange occurs through minor leakage and the opening and closing of the MTF access doors.
ET-30	Environmental control system provides for heating external air vented into the Service Section.	Inspection	Verified.
ET-40	Thermal control system provides a minimum of two coolant loops with different characteristics.	ROD	Verified.
ET-50	Thermal control system provides a coolant loop to the ISPR with specific characteristics.	Test	Verified.
ET-60	Thermal control system provides a coolant loop to the MTF air conditioning system with specific charac-	Test	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	teristics.		
ET-70	Thermal control system provides a water coolant loop to the FEG LED panels with specific characteristics.	Test	Verified.
ET-80	Thermal control system provides a coolant loop to an external heat rejection unit with specific characteristics.	ROD	Verified.
ET-90	Thermal control system provides a heat rejection unit.	ROD, Inspection	Verified.
ET-100	Heat rejection unit operates in temperatures ranging from -40 to +15°C	ROD	Although specified for these values testing down to -40°C was not completely possible during the Bremen AIT phase and these temperatures will only be seen during the overwintering phase in Antarctica. The only component exposed to these external temperatures is the freecooler, which has a very simplified design (two fans overtop of cooling fluid lines/radiators) and thus should be less likely to fail over this range than other more complicated systems.
ET-110	Thermal control system monitors and controls specific parameters.	ROD	Verified.
ET-120	Thermal control system provides sufficient coolant volume to allow the coolant loop to be refilled at least 3 times during the Antarctic operations phase.	Inspection	Verified. Ca. 180 L of Tyfoxit F50 was shipped to Antarctica (with each fill requiring ca. 45 L) while 90 L of Tyfocor-L was shipped to Antarctica (with each fill requiring ca. 30 L of 20% solution).
SS-2010	Service Section provides a Main Power Box for the distribution of the NM-III supplied 230 VAC into both 230 VAC lines and 24 VDC	Test	Verified. Certain 24 VDC, 12 VDC and 9 VDC sources are found outside of the power box.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	lines.		
SS-3010	Service Section provides a computer system and display for monitoring overall MTF system telemetry and issuing commands.	Inspection	Verified.
SS-3020	Service Section provides a computer system for monitoring FEG telemetry data and issuing commands.	Inspection	Verified.
SS-3030	Service Section provides a computer for commanding and monitoring the EDEN ISS ISPR.	Inspection	Verified.
SS-3040	Service Section provides video monitoring and video teleconferencing facilities.	Inspection	Verified.
SS-3050	MTF system-, EDEN ISS ISPR-, and FEG housekeeping data shall be made available to the MTF system monitor, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor, the ECC and applicable EDEN ISS User Home Bases.	Test	Verified.
SS-3060	Specific MTF system commands shall be executable from the MTF system monitors in the MTF Service Section, the Neumayer Station III EDEN ISS monitor and the ECC.	Test	Verified.
ISPR-1010	EDEN ISS ISPR system comprises an	System Level: ROD	Verified. Dimensions have high similarity to an International Standard Pay-

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	ISPR-like rack facility for the growth of consistently safe vegetable food in microgravity.		load Rack and P/L provided resources have high similarity to EDR MKII provisions.
ISPR-1020	ISPR has dimensions and shape similar to flight EDR2.	System Level: ROD	Verified. See close out of req. ISPR-1010.
ISPR-1030	ISPR has internal payload interfaces similar to EDR2 internal payload interfaces.	System Level: ROD	Verified. See close out of req. ISPR-1010.
ISPR-1040	ISPR houses 2 independently controlled plant cultivation modules.	System Level: ROD	Verified. The growth chambers have different dimensions to allow different crops growth, and are called Growth Chamber Short (GCS) and Growth Chamber Long (GCT).
ISPR-1050	ISPR system allows both remote and in situ monitoring and control activities.	System Level: ROD	Verified. A touch screen placed on the rack front panel displays real time telemetry, while it is possible real time remote monitoring via a LabVIEW generated Client software.
ISPR-2010	ISPR provides an atmospheric environment suitable for the growth of selected crops, controlling in selected acceptability ranges.	System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Analysis, Test	Verified. Refer to D4.1, Error! Reference source not found..
ISPR-2020	ISPR provides means to respond to environmental contingencies	System Level: ROD, Analysis Equipment Level: ROD, Analysis	Verified. Emergency electrical stop button available in visible position.
ISPR-2030	ISPR provides for the selected crop vital resources supply within defined acceptability range and quali-	System Level: ROD, Test	Verified. Refer to D4.1, Error! Reference source not found..

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	ty.	Equipment Level: ROD, Analysis, Test	
ISPR-2040	ISPR provides means to manage produced wastes.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. Produced wastes are used up filters and used up root modules (with substrate). All are accessible for removal and replacement, to be disposed together with other Neumayer III waste.
ISPR-2050	ISPR provides a system to maintain internal compartments pressure equal to the cabin atmosphere.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD, Analysis, Test	Verified. Barometric pressure sensors allow detection of pressure anomalies and actuation of pressure equalization means.
ISPR-3010	ISPR has fixed secondary structure for harness fixation during crane hoisting.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified.
ISPR-3020	ISPR tolerates an ambient temperature range of 16 – 30°C and relative humidity 25 – 70% during normal operations in the MTF.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. Refer to D4.1, Error! Reference source not found..
ISPR-3030	ISPR tolerates ambient temperature range of -10°C to +40°C, relative humidity of 20% to 70% without incurring structural or functional damage during non-operational transport phase.	System Level: Analysis Equipment Level: Analysis	Verified. No damages due to temperature observed after shipment to Antarctica.
ISPR-3040	ISPR is fixed to MTF wall and floor when in operation.	System Level: Review of Design, In-	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
		Inspection Equipment Level: Review of Design	
ISPR-3050	ISPR has 2 interfaces for mounting external equipment to the racks.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. ISPR primary structure is realized with Bosch Rexroth aluminum profiles that allow mounting of external equipment to the rack in multiple positions.
ISPR-3060	ISPR has a mass of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - rack primary structure < 150 kg - payload < 450 kg. 	System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Analysis, Test	Verified. Total ISPR rack weight is 487 kg.
ISPR-3070	ISPR provides a Utility Interface Panel (UIP) for resource connections similar to that defined in [RD2], Figure 3.3-5.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found..
ISPR-3080	ISPR uses COTS mechanical hardware to the maximum extent possible (i.e. including standard lockers and drawers as foreseen for EDR-2 subsystems).	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.5". ISPR primary structure is realized mainly with Bosch Rexroth aluminum profiles and accessories.
ISPR-3090	ISPR provides a connector interface for provision of CO ₂ to the Growth Chamber Modules via an external gas cylinder.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level:	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found..

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
		ROD	
ISPR-3100	ISPR provides a connector interface for provision of fresh water to the ISPR nutrient delivery system.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found..
ISPR-3110	ISPR provides a connector for sampling of fluid from the ISPR nutrient delivery system.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found..
ISPR-3120	ISPR provides a vent for removal of waste gases to MTF atmosphere.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.5". The PCDH drawer FAN vents in the back of the drawer in a portion not isolated from the MTF atmosphere.
ISPR-3130	ISPR provides a LAN connector interface.	System Level: ROD Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found..
ISPR-4010	ISPR shall use < 2 kW electrical power.	System Level: ROD, Test Equipment Level: ROD, Test	Verified. ISPR uses < 1 kW electrical power.
ISPR-4020	ISPR shall use the 230 VAC provided by the Neumayer Station III.	System Level: ROD, Test Equipment Level:	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
		ROD	
ISPR-4030	ISPR 230 VAC to 24 VDC power converter shall comply with the electrical characteristics in [RD3] section 3.2.	System Level: ROD, Test Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-4040	ISPR shall provide a 230 VAC to the LED panel Power Supply Unit (PSU). The PSU shall convert to 48 VDC for the LED and CPU. Variable power output to the LED shall be controlled via the CPU.	System Level: ROD, Test Equipment Level: ROD	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-4050	ISPR shall have a dedicated panel providing manual switches/display to control main power switch, single drawer power switches etc.	System Level: ROD, Test Equipment Level: ROD, Test	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.). This is possible via the touch screen in the front section.
ISPR-5010	ISPR shall use cooling water supplied by the MTF with a fixed flow rate < 190 kg/h and temperature 16 – 20°C.	System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Analysis	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-5020	ISPR shall return coolant water to the MTF environmental control system with a temperature <25°C.	System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Analysis	Verified. Refer to MTF telemetry.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
ISPR-5030	ISPR shall assure that the delta pressure between the inlet and outlet quick disconnects is 40 kPa when ISPR operated at selected flow rate.	System Level: Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Analysis	Verified. Refer to ISPR telemetry.
ISPR-6010	ISPR shall rely either on LAN or RS232 interfaces for commanding and data collection of rack functions from the external C&DH system.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found.
ISPR-6020	ISPR shall rely on a local data acquisition and command board for the EDEN ISS payload sensors and actuators interaction.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found.
ISPR-7010	ISPR shall provide an illumination system to the payload cultivation modules comprising LED plates, LED plate mounting I/F etc.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found.
ISPR-7020	Plant Growth Chamber shall be illuminated by a single LED panel of maximum dimensions 60 x 40 x 7.5 cm.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found.
ISPR-7030	LED panel shall be water cooled via	System Level: Review of Design, Test	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	a cold-plate.	Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test	
ISPR-7040	LED panel shall be dimmable from 100 to 600 $\mu\text{moles/s/m}^2$.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-7050	Each LED panel shall be water cooled via the MTF Thermal Control System such that the maximum operating temperature of each does not exceed 40 °C.	Test	Verified. D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.) and ISPR telemetry.
ISPR-7060	Each LED panel shall have a control / power distribution box that accepts an Ethernet connector and 230 VAC power feed.	Inspection	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found.
ISPR-7070	Each LED panel shall be monitored for Status (Status), Set point per panel (S_450, S_660, S_735, S_5700) [2 byte integer] etc.	Test	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-8010	ISPR shall have a guarded, two-position, manually operated switch installed in a visible and accessible position on the front of each rack	System Level: Review of Design, Inspection, Test	Verified. See "ISPR Design Document-v0.6", Error! Reference source not found.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	that removes all power to the rack during maintenance and handling.	Equipment Level: Review of Design	
ISPR-8020	The ISPR shall provide the capability to control and monitor a smoke detector, control a red LED smoke indicator, and monitor the fan ventilation status as described in [RD2], 3.3.4.1.	System Level: Review of Design, Inspection, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design	Verified. No red LED smoke indicator present, RED blinking alarm on touch screen is displayed in case of positive signal from smoke detector.
ISPR-8030	ISPR shall be constructed from materials that are non-toxic and off gas no dangerous chemicals according to Neumayer Station III regulations.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design	Verified. Main material used are aluminum, stainless steel, ABD, PTFE, PP.
ISPR-8040	ISPR shall support fire suppression capability.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis	Verified. Suppression via CO2 extinguisher is possible.
ISPR-8050	ISPR parts shall be able to sustain application of the fire suppression method.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis	Verified. Suppression via CO2 extinguisher is possible.
ISPR-8060	ISPR shall provide means of restoration of the growth chamber envi-	System Level: Review of Design	Verified. Venting after use of CO2 extinguisher is possible.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	ronment, at least to reach degraded conditions.	Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis	
ISPR-8070	When electrical, biological, optical, sharp edges/points, or other hazards are identified by safety personnel, an appropriate label shall be applied in a prominent location.	System Level: Review of Design, Inspection Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis, Inspection	Verified.
ISPR-9010	2 Plant Growth Chambers (including root module, illumination module and atmosphere management module) shall have the following enveloping dimensions: Small growth chamber: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 460 mm wide - 720 mm deep - 390 mm high Large growth chamber: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 460 mm wide - 720 mm deep - 830 mm high. 	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9020	Internal surfaces of the plant cultivation modules shall be highly re-	System Level: Review of Design	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.).

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	flective.	Equipment Level: Review of Design	
ISPR-9030	ISPR shall provide a nutrient delivery system (NDS) to the payload cultivation modules that supports nutrient storage, water storage (DI or humidity condensate) etc.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9040	NDS shall be composed of : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient distribution system - Nutrient storage system The Nutrient storage system shall be divided into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient Storage (NS) - Water Storage (WS) - Acid/Base Storage (AS) Replenishment solutions Storage (RS-A, RS-B).	System Level: Review of Design, Inspection, Analysis, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9050	The acid storage, base storage and RS shall provide the amounts necessary for a full life cycle of the most requiring selected crop, considering humidity condensate recovering The NS shall be designed taking into account maximum growth cycle	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Analysis	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	uptake and contingency needs (2.1 times the growth cycle uptake). Long term storage shall not affect the risk of biological, chemical or particulate contamination.		
ISPR-9060	<p>The nutrient solution storage shall provide fluidic interfaces compatible with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Up to 4 replenishment/adjustment solutions^a, - Up to 2 DI/humidity condensate external supply^{a,b} - nutrient delivery system for root module periodical flushing - drain tank. <p>^aWater shall be supplied to points of use in conformance with the interface specifications for water temperature and quality.</p> <p>^bProcessed waste water shall meet specified quality requirements for further use.</p>	<p>System Level: Review of Design</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design, Inspection</p>	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9070	Root module shall provide the capability to dispose excess water through continuous recirculation and evaporation.	<p>System Level: Review of Design</p> <p>Equipment Level: Review of Design,</p>	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.).

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
		Inspection	
ISPR-9080	Acid storage, base storage, and replenishment solutions storage reservoirs shall allow draining activities (e.g. pressurizing port or pump interface).	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Inspection	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9090	Solutions storage reservoirs shall be designed as accessible for preventive complete replacement with spare equipment unit (ready to use, not included in the ISPR structure).	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Inspection	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9100	Nutrient delivery system shall be designed to provide its nominal performance both in continuous and in cyclic operation.	System Level: Analysis Equipment Level: Analysis, Test	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9110	Nutrient delivery system shall prevent solutions quality variations in case of long-term non-operative conditions for up to 1 month.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9120	Nutrient delivery system shall meet its performance requirements both in 1g and micro-g conditions.	System Level: Analysis, Test	Partially verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.). No test in microgravity was performed.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
		Equipment Level: Analysis	
ISPR-9130	ISPR shall provide for health and status monitoring of parameters of the payload cultivation modules such as nutrient solution: quantity level, EC, pH, temperature, root module: moisture level, EC, pH, temperature etc.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Test	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9140	ISPR shall provide for video monitoring of the payload cultivation chambers.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.). For data rate availability only pictures are taken (1/day per chamber)
ISPR-9150	ISPR shall support a monitoring method to identify microorganisms dangerous for crop health and food safety.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Analysis, Test	Verified. Sampling port is available for both nutrient solution and growth chamber air.
ISPR-9160	ISPR shall provide method(s) to monitor total microbiological contamination load in the growth chamber and in the liquid loop.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Review of Design	Verified. Sampling port is available for both nutrient solution and growth chamber air.
ISPR-9190	ISPR shall provide methods to prevent microbiological contamination of surfaces in the growth chamber	System Level: Review of Design, Test	Verified. Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.). Filters are present in the fluid loops. Special materials have been selected for the nutrient solutions reservoirs.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	and in the fluid loops.	Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis	
ISPR-9180	ISPR shall provide methods to mitigate microbiological contamination of surfaces and fluids, while avoiding chemical contaminating residues.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis	Verified. See close-out of ISPR-9180.
ISPR-9190	ISPR shall provide methods to remove ethylene and other trace chemical contaminants.	System Level: Review of Design Equipment Level: Analysis, Test	Filters are present in the air loop.
ISPR-9200	ISPR shall provide prevention of cross-contamination (trace gas, bacteria, viruses, particulate) between different growth volumes, and between growth volumes and crew compartment.	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.). Filters are present in the air loop.
ISPR-9210	ISPR shall provide a controlled environment to the shoot zone of the plant growth chamber, as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • O₂ = 21% to 24% % • CO₂ = 200-1000 ± 50 ppm • Ethylene (produced by plants) less than 50 ppb 	System Level: Review of Design, Test Equipment Level: Review of Design, Analysis	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.) and D4.1 (ISPR Test Results, Error! Reference source not found.).

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TGCS. = 24°C ± 1.5°C • TGCT = 26°C ± 1.5°C • RH = 70% ±15 % • Air flow = 0.3-0.7 ± 0.1 m/s • Light level = 100-600 ± 50 μmol/m²/s <p>P = 1.0 ±0.1 bar</p>		
ISPR-9220	<p>The following materials are non-desirable in the plant cultivation chambers and should be avoided for structural components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polyethylene - Metallic coatings such as brass, copper, zinc - Plastics with high level of plasticizers or non-healthy plasticizers such as butyl-phthalates - PVC <p>Styrofoam bits</p>	Inspection	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.).
ISPR-9230	<p>The following materials shall be used as far as possible for surfaces in the plant cultivation chambers that are in contact with water:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stainless steel - Glass - Teflon 	Inspection	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.).

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polypropylene Baked enamels		
ISPR-9240	The following materials shall be avoided in the plant cultivation chamber materials if ozone is to be used as bacterial sterilizer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Buna-N (Nitrile) - Natural rubber - Nylon - Steel (mild, HSLA) ▶ Zinc 	Inspection	Not applicable. ISPR does not use ozone sterilization.
ISPR-9250	The Plant Growth Chamber drawers shall be removable from the ISPR.	Inspection	Verified. See D3.7 (ISPR Design Document, Error! Reference source not found.).
FEG-1010	FEG shall be housed in a standard 20-foot high-cube container.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-1020	FEG shall provide a transparent access door from the service container and an emergency exit door at the other end.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-1030	FEG emergency exit door shall be dimensioned to allow personnel in emergency climate protection clothing to exit without hindrance.	Inspection, Demonstration	Verified. Full sized door used.
FEG-1040	FEG shall have provision for a set of climate protection clothing near the emergency exit door.	Inspection	Reference S-240.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
FEG-1050	FEG shall provide a seed germination and initial growth phase facility (nursery).	Inspection	Verified. Nursery situated at the L4 position in the FEG.
FEG-3010	Environmental control system shall actively control overall FEG ambient atmospheric parameters at canopy level including temperature 16 – 30 °C, relative humidity 70+/-5%, air flow plant growth units: 0.4 m/s (target).	Test	Verified.
FEG-3020	Environmental control system shall monitor and control the concentration of ambient atmosphere parameters in the FEG including ppCO ₂ , ppO ₂ , relative humidity, temperature, air flow rate, pressure differential.	Test	Although a sensor in the atmospheric management system monitors O ₂ , ppO ₂ is not actively controlled.
FEG-3030	Environmental control system shall remove and filter FEG ambient atmospheric trace contaminants, particulates, and microbial contamination.	Test	Verified. Coarse filters, carbon filters and HEPA filters installed in the air management system.
FEG-3040	Temperature, relative humidity, CO ₂ , and light sensors shall be deployed inside the FEG in order to have punctual measurements of these parameters.	Inspection, Test	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
FEG-4010	FEG science telemetry parameters to be monitored by the data handling system shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Test	Verified.
FEG-4020	FEG environmental data parameters to be monitored by the data handling system shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Test	Verified.
FEG-4030	FEG LED Panel data parameters to be monitored by the data handling system shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Test	Verified.
FEG-4040	FEG nutrient delivery system data parameters to be monitored by the data handling system shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Test	Verified.
FEG-4050	FEG Environmental Control System commands that are executable from the system monitors in the MTF, Neumayer Station III, the DLR Control Center and applicable remote users shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Soft-	Test	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	ware Interface Control Document.		
FEG-4060	FEG lighting system commands that are executable from the system monitors in the MTF, Neumayer Station III, the DLR Control Center and applicable remote users shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Test	Verified.
FEG-4070	FEG nutrient delivery system commands that are executable from the system monitors in the MTF, Neumayer Station III, the DLR Control Center and applicable remote users shall be according to deliverable document D2.3, Software Interface Control Document.	Test	Verified.
FEG-4080	FEG shall provide video monitoring and video teleconferencing facilities.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-5010	Total power consumption for the LED lighting of each plant tray shall not exceed 240 W.	Test	Verified. The high growth racks have installed power supply with a maximum of 240 W (short grow racks have a max of 120 W).
FEG-5020	LED panels shall provide lighting with light emission spectra tailored to specific requirements of the plants to be grown.	Test	Verified. Primary light settings defined during the Bremen AIT phase.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
FEG-5030	LED panels shall each have four LED channels that can be individually dimmed. The LEDs shall be made up of sets of 450 nm, 660 nm, 735 nm and 5700K LEDs.	Test	Verified.
FEG-5040	LED panels shall provide the following PAR capability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tall plants up to $600 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ - short plants up to $300 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ - nursely 200 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ 	Test	Verified.
FEG-5050	Each plant tray will have a single LED panel.	Test	Verified.
FEG-5060	Each LED panel shall have a temperature sensor and over temperature protection.	Test	Verified.
FEG-5070	Each LED panel shall be water cooled via the MTF Thermal Control System such that the maximum operating temperature of each panel does not exceed 50 °C.	Test	Verified.
FEG-5080	Each LED panel shall have a control / power distribution box that accepts an Ethernet connector and 48	Not to be verified. See comment.	Feeding each LED panel with 230 VAC (the internal conversion done within the LED is actually irrelevant on the system level and can be left out of this document).

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	VDC power feed.		
FEG-5090	<p>Each LED panel shall be monitored for the following parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Status per panel LED (Status) - Set point per panel LED (S_450, S_660, S_735, S_5700) [2 byte integer] - Temperature per bar in the panel LED (T1, T2, T3) [2 byte integer] 1/10 degC - Current per bar LED (I1, I2, I3) [2 byte integer] milliamp - HW configuration LED HW_config [String] - FW version LED FW_version [String] 	Test	Although not all directly employed in nominal operations, this data is available.
FEG-6010	Specific AMS control sensor signals shall be used to provide critical environmental data to the overall MTF Caution and Warning system monitoring. Personnel shall be alerted when ambient monitored parameters exceed allowed limits. These safety related AMS sensor signals shall be in addition to the MTF stand-alone safety system.	Inspection, Test	Verified.
FEG-7010	FEG plant growing facilities shall comprise two rows of plant grow racks, one row each along the long	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	walls of the container.		
FEG-7020	Plant grow racks shall each be bolted to load bearing points on the container walls and floor and assure there is 8.5 cm free space on the rear side for air ducts and utility lines.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-7030	Plant grow trays shall have maximum dimensions of (footprint): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 60 cm length - 40 cm width 	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-7040	Each plant grow rack shall be able to accommodate up to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 plant grow trays with a growth height of 24 cm - 4 plant grow trays with a growth height of 76 cm - 2 plant grow trays with a growth height of 180 cm. 	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-7050	Each plant grow tray shall provide the following facilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - light tight enclosure providing at least 5 cm height for plant roots - interchangeable lid with holes to optimize crop spacing - LED panel 	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	water/nutrient feeder lines and return lines		
FEG-7060	The plant grow racks shall be constructed using materials that do not corrode in the humidity/temperature environment of the FEG or release chemicals hazardous to human health.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-7070	The plant grow racks shall be constructed such that the plant root compartment is sealed as much as possible to the external environment.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-7080	<p>Following materials are non-desirable in the plant cultivation modules and should be avoided for structural components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polyethylene - Metallic coatings such as brass, copper, zinc - Plastics with high level of plasticizers or non-healthy plasticizers such as butyl-phthalates - PVC - Styrofoam bits 	Inspection	Verified. That said, much of the hard plastic piping in the MTF is made from PVC. There was an original suggestion to avoid using PVC as this was named in several Antarctic Treaty documents but because the project will be pulling out all of the installed hardware following the Antarctic operations phase (save buried cables and legs of the external platform), the use of PVC for the nutrient delivery system and thermal system piping was permitted (no negative effects themselves on plant growth).
FEG-7090	Following materials shall be used as far as possible for surfaces in the	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	plant cultivation modules that are in contact with water: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stainless steel - Glass - Teflon - Polypropylene - Baked enamels 		
FEG-7100	Following materials shall be avoided in the plant cultivation modules materials if ozone is to be used as bacterial sterilizer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Buna-N (Nitrile) - Natural rubber - Nylon - Steel (mild, HSLA) - Zinc 	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-7110	Cameras for monitoring shall be installed to view each plant tray shelf to monitor plant growth.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-8010	NDS shall continuously supply pre-defined water/nutrient mix to the plant growth units when activated.	Test	Verified.
FEG-8020	NDS shall provide the capability to house 2 different bulk nutrient solutions and to distribute these solutions to each individual tray within the FEG.	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
FEG-8030	NDS shall provide capability to manually resupply micro- and macronutrients, water.	Inspection	Verified. But this cannot be conducted on individual micro or macronutrient levels.
FEG-8040	NDS shall be activated/deactivated either manually or remotely by telecommand.	Test	Verified.
FEG-8050	NDS shall provide the water and nutrients directly to the plant roots in the plant growth units using an aeroponic and/or hybrid aeroponic/nutrient film technique system.	Test, Inspection	Verified.
FEG-8060	NDS shall provide sensors and sensor logic for monitoring all the parameters defined in command and data handling requirements.	Inspection, Test	Verified.
FEG-8070	NDS shall support the capability to accept and implement the software commands defined in command and data handling requirements.	Inspection, Test	Verified.
FEG-8080	NDS shall use the following nutrient chemical components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - NH_4NO_3 - $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{FeN}_3\text{NaO}_{10}$ (Fe-chelate DTPA) - CaCl_2 - KNO_3 - MgSO_4 	Inspection	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mg(NO₃)₂·7H₂O - K₂SO₄ - KH₂PO₄ - MnSO₄·H₂O - ZnSO₄·7H₂O - Na₂B₄O₇·10H₂O - CuSO₄·5H₂O - Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O 		
FEG-8090	<p>NDS shall autonomously control the nutrient pH using the following chemicals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nitric acid - Potassium hydroxide 	Test	Verified.
FEG-8100	NDS shall assure that no pathogens accumulate in the system particularly on critical items such as pipe joints, valves and tanks.	Not to be verified. See comment	This requirement is not possible to meet at 100% - and thus requirement FEG-8120 is sufficient to see that we are disinfecting to the extent possible, but there may still – as is almost always the case – something living in your hydroponic solution.
FEG-8110	FEG shall provide for the recycling of water/nutrients to the maximum extent possible.	N/A, Inspection ('to the extent possible' not verifiable)	Verified.
FEG-8120	NDS shall provide a disinfection system for recycling used liquid back to the plant growth units.	Inspection	Verified. Integrated ozone system built into the NDS racks.
FEG-8130	NDS shall provide for waste liquid disposal by draining to MTF waste tank.	Inspection, Test	Verified.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
FEG-8140	Service Section shall house two 250 L tanks for storage of bulk nutrient solution for the FEG plant trays.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-8150	Cold Porch sub-floor shall house a 250 to 300 L tank for storage of fresh water.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-8160	Cold Porch sub-floor shall house a 250 to 300 L tank for storage of waste water.	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-8170	NDS shall provide for easy sampling and analysis of the bulk as well as waste nutrient solutions.	Inspection, Test	Verified.
FEG-8180	NDS shall include sensors that permit the offline measurement of the following parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - pH - EC - Select nutrient ions 	Inspection	Adjusted.
FEG-8190	NDS shall recirculate the 'same' primary nutrient solution (with appropriate adjustment) for a minimum period of 4 weeks.	Test	Verified. Much longer periods observed during the AIT test phase.
FEG-8200	Following materials are non-desirable in the NDS and should be avoided for structural components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polyethylene 	Inspection	Verified. See response to FEG-7080.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metallic coatings such as brass, copper, zinc - Plastics with high level of plasticizers or non-healthy plasticizers such as butyl-phthalates - PVC - Styrofoam bits 		
FEG-8210	<p>Following materials shall be used as far as possible for surfaces in the NDS that are in contact with water:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stainless steel - Glass - Teflon - Polypropylene - Baked enamels 	Inspection	Verified.
FEG-8220	<p>Following materials shall be avoided in the NDS materials if ozone is to be used as bacterial sterilizer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Buna-N (Nitrile) - Natural rubber - Nylon - Steel (mild, HSLA) - Zinc 	Inspection	Verified.
FQ-10	<p>Following plant quality “quick-test” analyses shall be performed at Neumayer Station III / MTF:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chlorophyll content 	Test	Verified. Required measurement devices available in Antarctica.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Colour - Nitrate concentration - Index of refraction (Brix%) - Firmness/ripeness (penetrometer) - Horticultural measurements 		
FQ-20	FEG plants and growth parameters including illumination and nutrient mix shall be replicated in home laboratories.	Inspection	Verified.
FQ-30	Analytical procedures shall be developed for determining the following food quality parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Carbohydrates - Organic acids - Nutraceuticals (fibre, vitamins, polyphenols, flavonoids, anthocyanins, glucosinolates, carotenoids, chlorophylls) - Minerals - Fats - Anti-nutritionals (NO₃, oxalic acid) - Others 	Test	Verified. Primary analysis done in home laboratories.
FQ-40	Certain harvested food shall be checked for the following common pathogens: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total microbial count - Lactic acid bacteria 	Test	Verified. Food safety supplies and lab equipment available on-site in Antarctica.

Requirement ID	Requirement Brief Description	Verification Method	Verification Close-out
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Molds and yeasts - Total coliforms - Escherichia coli - Salmonella - Staphylococci 		
FQ-50	Food quality and safety samples for transport to home laboratories shall be freeze dried and stored at room temperature over the Antarctic deployment until return to European laboratories.	Inspection	Verified.
FQ-60	Some food harvested for human consumption shall after decontamination be stored in bio-degradable, sealing bags with a controlled passive atmosphere.	Inspection	Not verified. EDEN-ISS project at NM-III does not have such bags and thus it is not possible to accomplish this during first year of operations.
PHM-010	The FEG plant cultivation shall produce > 150 kg of fresh weight per year.	N/A. Requirement to be considered as guideline.	Verified via measurement during the Bremen AIT test phase.

Table 0-1: EDEN ISS System Requirements Verification Control Table

